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D7.8 Collection of Sectoral Transformation Policy Papers

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Preface

The NDC ASPECTS project will provide inputs to the Global Stocktake under the Paris Agreement (PA) and support the potential revision of existing Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) of the PA's parties, as well as development of new NDCs for the post 2030 period. The project will focus on four sectoral systems that are highly relevant in terms of the greenhouse gas emissions they produce, yet have thus far made only limited progress in decarbonization. To advance these transformations will require to understand and leverage the Eigenlogic of those systems and take into account specific transformation challenges. These sectors are transport & mobility (land-based transport and international aviation & shipping), emission intensive industries, buildings, and agriculture, forestry & land-use, including their supply by and interaction with the energy conversion sector.

D7.8 Collection of Sectoral Transformation Policy Papers

1. Changes with respect to the DoA

No changes with respect to the DoA

2. Dissemination and uptake

The main aim of this deliverable is to document the progress of the policy paper series during the first reporting period. All papers produced so far were already published individually on the project's website and advertised in the project newsletter and on social media.

3. Short Summary of results (<250 words)

As per the DoA, the project established a specific document template and style guide for the policy paper series as well as a chief editor. So far, two policy papers were published, plus a submission to the Global Stocktake (GST) process of the UNFCCC. As the project is starting to produce more research outputs, there will correspondingly be more material to translate into policy papers. The DoA already contains a detailed timeline for the future development of the policy paper series.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

This report.

LIST OF PARTICIPANTS

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2	Vrije Universiteit Brussel	VUB	Belgium	VUB BRUSSELS SCHOOL OF GOVERNANCE
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5	E3-MODELLING S.A.	E3M	Greece	E3 Modelling Energy Economy Environment
6	Asociación BC3 Basque Centre for Climate Change – Klima Aldaketa Ikergai	BC3	Spain	bc3 BASQUE CENTRE FOR CLIMATE CHANGE Klima Aldaketa Ikergai Sustainability, that's it!
7	Ita-Suomen Yliopisto	UEF	Finland	UNIVERSITY OF EASTERN FINLAND
8	Indian Institute of Management	IIMA	India	IIMA AMBA ACCREDITED
9	University of Cape Town	UCT	South Africa	UNIVERSITY OF CAPE TOWN IYUNIVESITHI YASAKAPA - UNIVERSITEIT VAN KAAPSTAD
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1 Background and Objective of the Policy Paper Series

Most outputs of work packages 1 to 6 will consist of research reports and manuscripts for academic journals. The objective of the policy paper series is therefore to distil policy-relevant results in a more digestible format targeted at policymakers and stakeholders.

2 Implementation so far

As per the DoA, the project established a specific document template and style guide for the policy paper series. In addition, Christof Arens (Wuppertal Institute) was designated as chief editor of the policy paper series with the task to engage with the corresponding scientific authors to assist and guide their writing efforts.

The first policy paper was published in October 2021 under the title “Maximising the Impact of the Global Stocktake: Options for Design and Implementation”. The policy brief aims to contribute to identifying how the Global Stocktake could be organised so as to maximise the effectiveness of the collective process towards achieving the goals of the Paris Agreement.

The second policy paper was published in September 2022 under the title “Article 6 and CORSIA after Glasgow: Ready for take-off?” The paper discusses interlinkages between the Carbon Offsetting and Reduction Scheme for International Aviation (CORSIA) of the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) on the one hand and the cooperative mechanisms under Article 6 of the Paris Agreement on the other. The paper identifies risks to the environmental integrity of CORSIA and Article 6 that could arise from these interlinkages and suggests potential remedies.

The policy briefs can be found on the NDC ASPECTS website¹ and are attached to this report.

In addition, WP1 produced a submission of project results to the Global Stocktake.² This submission essentially also has the form of a policy paper, even if it is not formally included in the policy paper series.

¹ <https://ndc-aspects.eu/publications/policy-briefs>

² http://ndc-aspects.eu/sites/default/files/2022-08/NDC%20ASPECTS_D1-1-GST%20submission_20220805.pdf

3 Future Planning

As the project is starting to produce more research outputs, there will correspondingly be more material to translate into policy papers. The DoA already contains a detailed timeline for the future development of the policy paper series as follows:

- MS7-10: Draft policy papers on specific issues of interest in the industry, transport, buildings and AFOLU sectors by M27; the specific issues of interest are to be determined over the course of the Sectoral Conversations conducted in WP1;
- MS47-50: Draft policy paper on sectoral governance gaps and options to overcome them in the industry, transport, buildings and AFOLU sectors by M24;
- MS35-38: Draft policy paper describing the content of sectoral transformations required to reach the Paris Agreement objectives and highlighting key priorities for international cooperation in the industry, transport, buildings and AFOLU sectors by M28;
- MS51: Three draft policy papers on sectoral climate club proposals by M30.

PARTICIPANTS

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Policy Brief

Maximising the Impact of the Global Stocktake:
Options for Design and Implementation

Issue #01 / October 2021

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Key messages

- The collective nature of the Global Stocktake (GST) does not allow for a Party-by-Party discussion of progress and options for the way forward. Nonetheless, the consideration of progress could be disaggregated in other ways to make best use of the rich and comprehensive information collected by breaking it down into manageable pieces. A sectoral approach to the GST would be especially useful in this regard, as sectors constitute the communities of action which climate policy needs to address. Moreover, each sector has distinct opportunities and challenges. Organising the GST to accommodate a sectoral approach would help reveal collective sectoral ambition gaps, highlight additional mitigation potentials and promote knowledge and learning on how to tap into these potentials. Involvement of sectoral ministries would amplify these effects.
- While the Paris Agreement and Decision 19/CMA.1 do not provide an explicit entry point for a sectoral approach, it could nevertheless be pursued under several of the broadly formulated ‘guiding questions’ listed in the revised non-paper by the Subsidiary Body Chairs.
- To ensure procedural fairness and boost transparency and accountability, equitable access should be guaranteed for developing country government delegations and different stakeholder groups. Equitable treatment of non-Party stakeholders’ inputs and perspectives includes early communication of time frames and procedures.
- To strengthen the follow-up of the GST outcomes, GST cycles should culminate in a high-level event at the level of heads of state and government, and an associated COP decision and/or declaration acknowledging the Paris Agreement’s long-term goal, stating collective overall and collective sectoral climate ambition and committing to further action needed. The core of a detailed technical summary of available options, best practices and recommendations could be recommendations for sectoral decarbonisation targets and roadmaps.

Introduction

The five-yearly Global Stocktake (GST) plays an essential role in the overall ambition mechanism of the Paris Agreement on climate change by ‘assess[ing] the collective progress towards achieving the purpose of this Agreement and its long-term goals’.¹ With the GST, Parties have created a mechanism through which they can collectively assess whether their ambitions and actions to achieve the Paris objectives are aligned with the latest scientific insights. The outcome of the GST ‘shall inform Parties in updating and enhancing, in a nationally determined manner, their actions and support in accordance with the relevant provisions of this Agreement, as well as in enhancing international cooperation for climate action’.²

¹ Paris Agreement, Article 14(1).

² Paris Agreement, Article 14(3).

Decision 19/CMA.1, adopted as part of the Paris Rulebook in 2018, distinguishes three components of the GST:

- *Information collection and preparation (GST-ICP)*, in which a wide range of inputs from both Parties and other stakeholders are compiled and synthesised.
- *Technical assessment (GST-TA)*, through which the information collected would be discussed and assessed; this component is supposed to revolve around an open, inclusive, transparent and facilitative ‘technical dialogue’, addressing the three main thematic areas of mitigation, adaptation and means of implementation, as well as the cross-cutting areas of impacts of response measures and loss and damage.
- A high-level *consideration of output (GST-CO)*, in which the outcomes of the other two components are discussed at high-level events, and which may result in the adoption of a CMA decision and/or a declaration.

While Decision 19/CMA.1 thus sets out the broad parameters for the design and implementation of the GST, it does not provide all the necessary details of how the process will be organised. To offer clarity in this respect, the Chairs of the Subsidiary Body for Scientific and Technological Advice (SBSTA) and the Subsidiary Body for Implementation (SBI) have been requested to ‘develop guiding questions for all components of the global stocktake, including specific thematic and cross-cutting questions’ and to ‘organize the global stocktake in a flexible and appropriate manner, to work on identifying opportunities for learning-by-doing, including for assessing collective progress, and to take the necessary steps for the consideration of inputs as they become available’.³

With the GST-ICP due to start at COP26 in Glasgow,⁴ there is an urgent need to identify how the GST could be organised so as to maximise the effectiveness of the process. Specifically, there is a need to better understand how the GST can influence national policymaking processes so as to increase ambition. In this policy brief, we apply the concept of the governance functions of international institutions to contribute to this understanding. While we recognise the importance and interrelatedness of all three thematic areas of the GST, this policy brief focuses on mitigation. However, to strengthen collective climate ambition, it will be important to link the GST outcomes of all three thematic areas (mitigation, adaptation and means of implementation).

Governance Functions of the Global Stocktake

The GST is an international governance mechanism with a dual nature: it is both (1) an evaluative system, as the GST assesses the collective performance towards a benchmark (the long-term goals of the Paris Agreement); and (2) a decision-making/communication process of the Parties consisting of a series of events taking place over a period of two years.

³ Decision 19/CMA.1, Matters Relating to Article 14 of the Paris Agreement and Paragraphs 99–101 of Decision 1/CP.21, FCCC/PA/CMA/2018/3/Add.2 (19 March 2019), paragraphs 7 and 16.

⁴ ‘Preparing for the First Global Stocktake: Revised Non-Paper by the Chairs of the SBSTA and SBI’ (15 September 2021), https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/REV_Non-paper_on_Preparing_for_GST1_forSBs_15Sept.pdf.

To analyse how the GST may best serve to catalyse the enhancement of actions and support, this brief builds on previous scholarship on the potential functions and effects of global governance. International institutions may employ a range of governance functions to help address problems such as climate change. The GST may in particular contribute to three governance functions as summarised in the table below.⁵

Governance Function	Description	Key Features and Main Added Value
Guidance and Signal	International institutions can signal the resolve of members to pursue a certain course of action; these signals derive from the principles and objectives on which such institutions are based, which can provide direction beyond the institution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agreement on principles and objectives • Helps align actors across countries and governance levels
Transparency and Accountability	International institutions may enhance the transparency of the actions taken by their members by collecting and analysing relevant data, and identifying and addressing problems in implementation of agreed rules and standards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reporting, review, compliance • Contributes to reciprocity, effective implementation and mutual trust
Knowledge and Learning	International institutions may create knowledge as well as platforms for individual and social learning. The aim is creation and diffusion of scientific, economic, technical and policy-related knowledge on the understanding of and/or possible solutions to the problem at hand	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation and collective appraisal of information and knowledge • Policy learning • Improved and shared understanding • Improved policies

These functions can be related to the three guiding questions that were used to structure the 2018 Talanoa Dialogue. ‘Where are we now’ relates to the function of transparency and accountability; ‘where do we need to go’ relates to the guidance and signal function; and ‘how do we get there’ involves knowledge and learning.⁶

These governance functions can be achieved not only through the potential outputs of the GST, such as a COP decision and/or a political declaration, but also through the very process of the GST. Overall, the extent to which these governance functions are fulfilled determines the extent to which the GST may affect relevant behaviour and enable Parties as well as non-Party stakeholders to strengthen their climate ambitions. Conversely, the design and organisation of the GST influences the achievement of these governance functions.

Guidance and Signal – Where Do We Need to Go?

The GST is an opportunity to further strengthen and refine the guidance and signal stemming from the Paris Agreement. The Agreement’s long-term temperature goal, along with the goal to achieve greenhouse gas neutrality in the second half of the century, provide a high-level, collectively agreed vision for global transformation. Re-

⁵ Sebastian Oberthür, Lukas Hermwille and Tim Rayner, ‘A Sectoral Perspective on Global Climate Governance: Analytical Foundation’ (2021) 8 *Earth System Governance* 100104. Two additional governance functions – (1) setting rules to facilitate collective action and (2) capacity building, technology and finance – are not covered here as they are less relevant in the GST context and are covered by other elements of the international climate regime.

⁶ Wolfgang Obergassel, Lukas Hermwille, Anne Siemons and Hannah Förster, ‘Success Factors for the Global Stocktake under the Paris Agreement’ (Wuppertal Institute 2019).

fining the signal provided by the Paris Agreement could not only help guide the strengthening of existing and development of new NDCs, but could also serve as an updated reference point for a variety of initiatives (including by non-state and subnational actors) and help channel attention to the challenges that need to be overcome on the ground. Further concretising the benchmark against which collective progress will be assessed periodically in the light of the most recent science, the GST can re-iterate and strengthen the signals sent by the Paris Agreement and thereby contribute to the normalisation of ambitious climate action and shift expectations of stakeholders across all governance levels.⁷ For example, the GST could pick up on the recent wave of ‘net-zero by 2050’ announcements, which can be considered a further elaboration of the long-term goal of the Agreement and a concretisation of this goal in more specific terms. The GST could also work to unpack the relationship between the Paris Agreement’s long-term goals and short-term ambitions. For instance, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change Special Report on the 1.5°C limit considered that global carbon dioxide emissions need to be roughly halved by 2030 to maintain a reasonable chance of keeping below 1.5°C.⁸ If the GST was able to adopt such findings, it would significantly strengthen the guidance and signal sent by the Paris Agreement.

The GST could also endeavour to break the global mitigation objectives down to the individual emitting sectors and develop timelines and roadmaps for each sector to achieve (net) zero emissions.⁹ Sectors constitute communities of action by which goods and services are produced and thereby establish the arenas which international climate policy needs to address.¹⁰ Policies and measures that need to be implemented to achieve NDCs are mostly sectoral, and governments are largely organised along sectoral lines. The current global net-zero goal, however, provides no clarity about which sectors and actors must reduce their emissions to zero (or below) and the time frames within which the transition should occur. A sectoral breakdown of the Agreement’s global ambitions could provide better and more detailed guidance to sectoral actors.

The GST could also assess and/or endorse existing sectoral visions (e.g., from intergovernmental or transnational sectoral governance initiatives). Work in this direction is already underway for example in the Marrakech Partnership for Global Climate Action (MPGCA), where various sectoral ‘climate action pathways’ have been identified.¹¹ However, the linkage between these activities and the UNFCCC/Paris Agreement process could still be strengthened. Holding such discussions within the framework of the GST could enhance the impact on Parties’ policies. A possible link has already been established in the revised non-paper on the GST by the Subsidiary Body Chairs, which mentions working together with the High-Level Champions and the MPGCA.

In terms of process, it would be useful if the high-level consideration of output included an event at the level of heads of state and government. This would strengthen the guidance and signal function of the GST, amplifying

⁷ Lukas Hermwille, Anne Siemons, Hannah Förster and Louise Jeffery, ‘Catalyzing Mitigation Ambition under the Paris Agreement: Elements for an Effective Global Stocktake’ (2019) 19(8) *Climate Policy* 988–1001; Louise Jeffery, Anne Siemons, Hannah Förster, Christian Nissen, Lukas Hermwille and Nico Kreibich, ‘The Challenges of Assessing “Collective Progress”: Design Options for an Effective Global Stocktake Process under the UNFCCC’ (Umweltbundesamt 2021).

⁸ IPCC, ‘Summary for Policymakers’ in *Global Warming of 1.5°C* (IPCC 2018).

⁹ Lukas Hermwille, Anne Siemons, Hannah Förster and Louise Jeffery, ‘Catalyzing Mitigation Ambition under the Paris Agreement: Elements for an Effective Global Stocktake’ (2019) 19(8) *Climate Policy* 988–1001; Louise Jeffery, Anne Siemons, Hannah Förster, Christian Nissen, Lukas Hermwille and Nico Kreibich, ‘The Challenges of Assessing “Collective Progress”: Design Options for an Effective Global Stocktake Process under the UNFCCC’ (Umweltbundesamt 2021).

¹⁰ David G. Victor, Frank W. Geels and Simon Sharpe, ‘Accelerating the Low Carbon Transition: The Case for Stronger, More Targeted and Coordinated International Action’ (2019), <http://www.energy-transitions.org/content/accelerating-low-carbon-transition>.

¹¹ UNFCCC, ‘Climate Action Pathways’, https://unfccc.int/climate-action/marrakech-partnership/reporting-and-tracking/climate_action_pathways.

the messages for national policy agendas and indicating a reinforced political commitment of Parties to the Paris Agreement and its goals in the light of the latest available science. Such an event could highlight key outcomes of the GST process and involve the commitment by Parties to taking the outcomes into account in NDC updates and revisions. If it is not possible to include such commitments in a CMA decision, individual Parties could spell out such commitments in a separate political declaration. Likewise, in line with the increased focus of the UNFCCC process on non-Party actors, such actors could also be encouraged to publish a declaration acknowledging the GST outcomes and committing to increasing ambition where needed.

Transparency and Accountability – Where Are We Now?

Generally, high levels of transparency and accountability could be argued to contribute to enhanced trust, provide reassurance to parties, facilitate acknowledgement of efforts, and promote learning and common understanding. Furthermore, transparency and accountability are interrelated with the willingness to take on more ambitious commitments.

The GST aims at enhancing the transparency of Parties' collective action and points to collective implementation successes and deficits. Parties thus collectively account for the performance of their climate policies. The UNFCCC Secretariat has begun to compile inputs into the GST, including national reports and reviews available to date (e.g., national communications, inventory reports, biennial (update) reports, long-term low greenhouse gas emission development strategies). Although the GST is a collective process, the gathering of inputs offers an opportunity for observers to place individual Party actions in a collective context, and to generate crucial data and information

The objective to assess collective progress precludes an opportunity for 'naming and shaming' within the GST. Nevertheless, the GST could still provide a sounding board for the enhanced transparency framework under Article 13. If collective progress is discussed at the global level, a next question is what progress each country has made individually. Actors such as opposition parliamentarians or national-level NGOs could use data from the enhanced transparency framework and the public attention generated by the GST to hold their governments to account.¹²

If sectoral decarbonisation visions were developed through – or alternatively served as input into – the GST, as discussed under the guidance and signal function, they could be used to strengthen transparency and accountability. The GST could not only take stock of current and projected emissions levels at the global level, but it could also provide a disaggregated picture of the status and trends of sectoral mitigation efforts. Such a sectoral focus could for example highlight that the transport sector has been performing especially poorly compared to other sectors – with a relatively strong growth of emissions in the past and projected for the future – and therefore requires particular attention.¹³

¹² Lukas Hermwille, Anne Siemons, Hannah Förster and Louise Jeffery, 'Catalyzing Mitigation Ambition under the Paris Agreement: Elements for an Effective Global Stocktake' (2019) 19(8) *Climate Policy* 988–1001; Louise Jeffery, Anne Siemons, Hannah Förster, Christian Nissen, Lukas Hermwille and Nico Kreibich, 'The Challenges of Assessing "Collective Progress": Design Options for an Effective Global Stocktake Process under the UNFCCC' (Umweltbundesamt 2021).

¹³ Wolfgang Obergassel, Oliver Lah and Frederik Rudolph, 'Driving towards Transformation? To What Extent Does Global Climate Governance Promote Decarbonisation of Land Transport?' (2021) 8 *Earth System Governance* 100098.

Transparency and accountability are closely linked to procedural fairness. The information base for the assessment of what collective progress has been achieved must take into account contributions of developing countries with limited capacities and non-Party stakeholder inputs. To ensure effective participation, the GST process should therefore provide for equitable access for Parties and ideally also for different groups of stakeholders, as well as equitable treatment of their respective inputs and perspectives. This should include not only facilitating the meaningful participation of developing country government delegations, but also participation of non-Party stakeholders. Stakeholders from developing countries will also require support to effectively engage in producing inputs to reduce the risk of inputs being dominated by developed country research and civil society organisations.¹⁴ Procedural fairness also means that non-Party stakeholders should be informed as early as possible about the time frames and procedures to ensure that their inputs can be adequately considered in the GST-TA and thereby feed into the GST-CO. This would further allow such stakeholders to coordinate inputs and avoid duplication.

Knowledge and Learning – How Do We Get There?

The GST could be a peer-learning platform for how to undertake ambitious mitigation actions. For many sectors, there remains much ambiguity about what ambitious decarbonisation pathways could look like.¹⁵

The GST can enhance knowledge and learning in various ways. It collects, aggregates and disseminates information relevant to the assessment of the Parties' contribution to the Paris Agreement. Highlighting and discussing best practices could foster learning. In addition, a process to develop sectoral decarbonisation visions and/or to discuss already existing ones – as discussed under the guidance and signal function – and tracking their implementation – as discussed for the transparency and accountability function – could become an important knowledge-building exercise. Furthermore, the GST could assess and highlight how technological, financial, and policy innovations have reduced the costs of mitigation options and thereby identify mitigation opportunities since Parties adopted their most recent NDCs.¹⁶ This may help advance the implementation of climate policies and measures by Parties and individual actors, and may lead Parties to re-interpret their interests and adapt their policies, and ultimately increase ambition.

The GST should focus on opportunities and barriers for decarbonisation, in particular on the ongoing cost reduction of mitigation options as well as on the substantial non-climate benefits that may be achieved by ambitious climate action, such as reducing local air pollution. The GST should also highlight best practices and how they may be replicated. Again, a sectoral perspective would provide a useful lens for organising such discussions.

The synthesis reports prepared by the UNFCCC Secretariat and constituted bodies can play an important role in advancing sharing knowledge and advancing policy learning. Parties – especially those with limited resources and capacities – will hardly be able to digest all the information that is supposed to be drawn on in the GST. Beyond

¹⁴ Christian Holz, Tom Athanasiou and Sivan Kartha, 'Equity in the Global Stocktake and Independent Global Stocktake' (Climate Equity Reference Project 2019).

¹⁵ Manjana Milkoreit and Kate Haapala, 'The Global Stocktake: Design Lessons for a New Review and Ambition Mechanism in the International Climate Regime' (2019) 19 *International Environmental Agreements: Politics, Law and Economics* 89–106; Louise Jeffery, Anne Siemons, Hannah Förster, Christian Nissen, Lukas Hermwille and Nico Kreibich, 'The Challenges of Assessing "Collective Progress": Design Options for an Effective Global Stocktake Process under the UNFCCC' (Umweltbundesamt 2021).

¹⁶ R.R. Constantino, S.D. Wubet and S. Herz, 'Advancing Ambition Through Socially Beneficial Climate Action: Recommendations for the Talanoa Dialogue and Paris Rulebook' (Institute for Climate and Sustainable Cities and Sierra Club 2018).

such synthesis reports, the knowledge and learning function could also be strengthened by the direct involvement of independent experts, which could also help Parties process the information. The technical dialogue under the GST-TA would be an appropriate framework for integrating their participation.

Conclusions and Recommendations

The potential governance functions of the GST (guidance and signal, transparency and accountability, knowledge and learning) can be useful criteria for the detailed organisation of the GST. The following conclusions and recommendations are directed at strengthening the political impact of the GST.

A Sectoral Approach

- The outcomes of the GST should support the enhancement of climate protection actions and support. However, the collective nature of the GST does not allow for a Party-by-Party discussion of progress and options for the way forward. Nonetheless, the consideration of progress could be disaggregated in other ways to make best use of the rich and comprehensive information collected.
- A sectoral focus would be especially useful in this regard, as sectors constitute the communities of action which climate policy needs to address. In addition, each sector is distinct in its mitigation opportunities and challenges. A sectoral perspective could therefore strengthen all three governance functions of the GST, by: (1) providing for a clear signal to sectoral stakeholders (including government ministries, businesses and investors) by specifying sectoral visions, roadmaps and timetables, and/or discussing and potentially endorsing already existing ones; (2) highlighting the progress (or lack thereof) made by individual sectors, thus boosting transparency and accountability; and (3) allowing for the effective sharing of knowledge and information to foster learning about sectoral mitigation opportunities.
- Sectoral discussions with strong involvement of line ministries of Parties, independent experts and other non-Party stakeholders, particularly from relevant business and industry, would enable detailed information sharing and better allow for transformational learning. Sectoral discussions can dovetail with ongoing processes such as the MPGCCA to ensure that information-sharing and learning continues in between GST cycles.
- Although the Paris Agreement and Decision 19/CMA.1 do not provide an explicit entry point for a sectoral approach, a sectoral approach could nevertheless be pursued under several broadly formulated ‘guiding questions’ for the GST-ICP listed in the revised non-paper by the Subsidiary Body Chairs, including:
 - What information is needed for countries to strengthen domestic emissions reductions and removals in line with Paris Agreement goals and what recommendations can be developed to increase ambition? (Question 6).
 - What climate actions have been undertaken by non-Party stakeholders and UNFCCC observer organization and what has been their impact? Which ones have worked and what obstacles or barriers have been encountered? (Question 29).

- What opportunities can be seized to further bolster cooperation and support for mitigation and adaptation? (Question 32).¹⁷

Ensuring Procedural Fairness

- Effective participation by Parties and non-Party actors is important for all three governance functions. Equitable access may require dedicated support for the participation of Parties and non-Party stakeholders with lower capacities.
- Equitable access for Parties and different groups of stakeholders matters in all stages of the GST. To allow stakeholders to adequately prepare and coordinate, the upfront communication of time frames, procedures and other relevant information is key.

Strengthening Outcomes and Follow-up

- A dedicated high-level political event at the level of heads of state and government would strengthen the messages emerging from the GST and mark a major opportunity for Parties to strengthen their political commitment to the Paris Agreement and its goals in the light of the latest available science. The outcome – in the form of a CMA decision and/or a declaration – can further be accompanied by a mirroring declaration by non-Party stakeholders that would signal their willingness and ambitions to implement the GST outcomes.
- Recommendations and roadmaps for how sectoral decarbonisation targets could be achieved could be the core of a detailed technical summary of available options and best practices, and the final CMA decision and/or political declaration should engage with and endorse these results.

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¹⁷ See ‘Preparing for the First Global Stocktake: Revised Non-Paper by the Chairs of the SBSTA and SBI’ (15 September 2021), https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/REV_Non-paper_on_Preparing_for_GST1_forSBs_15Sept.pdf.

NDC ASPECTS

POLICY BRIEF

Maximising the Impact of the Global Stocktake: Options for Design and Implementation

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Policy Brief

Article 6 and CORSIA after Glasgow:
Ready for take-off?

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Key messages

- Aviation is one of the most challenging sectors to decarbonise. Although the Paris Agreement in principle covers emissions from all sectors, including those of aviation, most Parties to the Paris Agreement have not included emissions from international flights in their Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs). However, these emissions are explicitly addressed by the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO).
- In 2016, ICAO adopted a market-based mechanism – the Carbon Offsetting and Reduction Scheme for International Aviation (CORSIA) – to address the sector’s growth in emissions. In the meantime, Parties to the Paris Agreement in 2021 agreed on a detailed rulebook for market mechanisms under Article 6 of the Agreement, which creates linkages with CORSIA.
- We identify four types of interactions between CORSIA and Article 6 rules: (1) allowing Parties with single-year targets to use the averaging accounting approach creates a loophole that may undermine the environmental integrity of both CORSIA and Article 6; (2) the quality criteria for CORSIA offsets may be strengthened by following Article 6 rules; (3) the level of CORSIA’s ambition will affect the supply side of carbon credits, including those provided under Article 6; and (4) like CORSIA, the operation of Article 6 may rely on private certification standards’ registries.
- To ensure that CORSIA provides a meaningful contribution to climate change mitigation in the sector, we suggest that ICAO Member States should: (1) adopt a long-term climate target for the sector in line with the Paris Agreement, (2) revise its quality criteria for offset programmes, (3) address non-CO₂ effects, and (4) carry out an assessment of the impacts on the functioning of the Article 6 mechanisms each time a decision is made.
- Parties to the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change could also take specific action, including refining guidance on averaging, establishing a buffer pool to offset an increase in emissions, and considering a requirement for Parties to transition towards multi-year emission targets.

1. Introduction

Aviation is the most carbon-intensive mode of transport, with carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions having grown rapidly in recent decades (IEA, 2020). Since 2000, CO₂ emissions from commercial flights have increased by 50% (IEA, 2020). These emissions are projected to continue rising, with commercial aircraft emissions predicted to triple by 2050 (Overton, 2022). As a result of this projected emissions growth, the aviation industry could potentially consume 27% of the global carbon budget for 1.5 °C by 2050 (Pidcock and Yeo, 2016). While the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) and the Paris Agreement do not explicitly refer to international aviation emissions, they do not exclude them either. The Paris Agreement commits Parties to submit economy-wide absolute emission reduction targets as part of their Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs). However, most Parties have so far not included emissions from international flights in their NDCs (Murphy, 2020).

Instead, these emissions are directly addressed outside the UNFCCC process by a separate United Nations (UN) agency, the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO). The primacy of ICAO to address international aviation emissions was more or less confirmed by the omission of the sector in the Paris Agreement (Martinez Romera, 2016). As a specialised UN agency designed to address matters concerning international aviation, ICAO arguably represents the ‘appropriate forum’ to regulate emissions arising from the sector (ICAO, 2016: 1). In 2010, ICAO established the sector-wide goal of carbon-neutral growth from 2020 onwards (ICAO, 2010). In 2016, ICAO then adopted a market-based mechanism – the Carbon Offsetting and Reduction Scheme for International Aviation (CORSIA) – to address the sector’s large and rapidly rising emissions (ICAO, 2016). As the name suggests, CORSIA is a global offsetting scheme intended to complement other efforts to realise the sector-wide objective of carbon-neutral growth from 2020 (ICAO, 2010; ICAO, 2016). Under the scheme, aircraft operators are required to offset any increase in their CO₂ emissions.

While states were developing rules for a market-based mechanism for international aviation emissions, they were also negotiating rules to operationalise the Paris Agreement’s market mechanisms introduced in its Article 6. Although the majority of the ‘Paris rulebook’ was adopted in Katowice in 2018, negotiations on Article 6 were highly contentious, spilling over to the Glasgow Climate Conference (COP26) in 2021. At Glasgow, detailed guidance regarding Article 6 was finally agreed. Although originally envisioned to assist Parties in the implementation and achievement of their NDCs, the Article 6 rulebook creates linkages to CORSIA and the voluntary carbon market. Accordingly, this policy paper seeks to explore these linkages by analysing the interplay between the rules adopted under the Article 6 rulebook and CORSIA.

The paper proceeds in four steps. First, it presents an overview of CORSIA by outlining its offsetting requirements, eligibility criteria and implementation phases, as well as highlighting criticisms of the scheme (Section 2). Second, it provides an overview of the Article 6 rulebook (Section 3). In particular, this section explores the role of emissions accounting through the application of ‘corresponding adjustments’ to counter double claiming as one form of double counting. Third, it analyses the interactions between CORSIA and the Article 6 rules (Section 4). Specifically, this section discusses four key interactions and their associated challenges: (1) the use of single-year targets and the average accounting approach; (2) quality criteria for offsets; (3) the level of ambition in ICAO decision-making; and (4) the use of registries. For each of these issues, the paper offers suggestions on how to address these challenges. Lastly, the paper identifies opportunities for Paris Agreement Parties and ICAO Member States to manage the interplay on CORSIA and Article 6 (Section 5), before offering some conclusions (Section 6).

2. An overview of CORSIA

2.1 CORSIA explained

CORSIA is touted as the world’s first sector-wide scheme to pursue emissions reductions (ICAO, 2019a: 216). It aims to complement other in-sector efforts to stabilise emissions from international aviation, such as technological solutions and sustainable fuels (ICAO, 2016). Following the adoption of CORSIA in 2016, the ICAO Council – the organisation’s governing body – approved its associated Standards and Recommended Practices (SARPS) – i.e., the detailed rules – in 2018 (ICAO, 2018).

CORSIA requires airlines and other aircraft operators to offset any growth in CO₂ emissions from international flights above 2020 levels (ICAO, 2019b). Accordingly, operators must compensate for any increase in their emissions by purchasing offsets as so-called emissions units from other sectors. Under CORSIA, operators can only purchase carbon offsets from 'emissions unit programmes' (EUPs) that have been approved by the ICAO Council (ICAO, 2019b). In addition, operators can minimise their offsetting obligations by using CORSIA eligible fuels, which includes sustainable aviation fuels (SAFs, renewable or waste-derived), as well as lower-carbon aviation fuels (LAFs, fossil-based) (ICAO, 2018).

The ICAO Council's decision on what EUPs to approve is informed by a recommendation by an expert group known as the Technical Advisory Body (TAB). The TAB was established by the Council in March 2019 and is composed of 19 expert members. In addition to establishing the TAB, the ICAO Council also approved the 'terms of reference', setting out the mission and tasks of the TAB (ICAO, 2019c). The key role of the TAB is to assess and recommend what programmes should be eligible for use under CORSIA. When conducting an assessment, the TAB considers whether the EUPs adhere to the CORSIA emissions unit eligibility criteria (EUCs) (ICAO, 2019d).

In terms of implementation, CORSIA is divided into three phases: a pilot phase from 2021 to 2023; a first phase from 2024 to 2026; and a second phase from 2027 to 2035 (ICAO, 2019b). The pilot phase and first phase are both voluntary, i.e., only ICAO Member States that have agreed to partake in these phases will be subjected to offsetting requirements. The second phase is mandatory and requires all Member States to participate from 2027 unless they are exempt. These exemptions include least developed countries, small island developing states, landlocked developing countries and states with less than 0.5% of air traffic (ICAO, 2019b). Member States that are exempt may opt to volunteer in the second phase.

The industry body International Air Transport Association (IATA) estimates that in the period 2021–2035, CORSIA will mitigate around 2.5 billion tonnes of CO₂ (IATA, 2019). At the same time, the scheme has been subjected to criticism since its adoption. One common criticism concerns the lifespan of CORSIA and hence, its ability to achieve sizeable emission reductions and meaningful in-sector decarbonisation. While the objective of the scheme is to help realise the sector-wide goal of carbon-neutral growth from 2020, CORSIA is only in place until 2035. Accordingly, the International Coalition for Sustainable Aviation (ICSA) – a network of NGOs accredited as an official observer by ICAO – anticipates that CORSIA will only 'modestly reduce' the overall climate impact of international aviation (ICSA, 2018: 4). In addition, the scheme merely targets *growth* in emissions. Airline operators are only required to offset emissions above 2020 levels. There is no requirement to mitigate emissions beyond this. This is a severe limitation of the mechanism that could significantly hinder the ability of CORSIA to have a meaningful impact on the sector.

As part of its 41st Assembly in late 2022, however, ICAO is set to consider the adoption of a long-term climate target for international aviation. This will be crucial if the objectives of the Paris Agreement are to be achieved. It will be vitally important that CORSIA's current objective is revisited to ensure alignment with a long-term climate goal. Schneider and Wissner (2022) have offered some recommendations to this end, such as an ambitious goal of net-zero emissions by 2035 that includes the possibility for offsetting.

Another criticism stems from the rules concerning CORSIA eligible fuels. These rules require that any alternative fuel used to lower offsetting obligations deliver a minimum emission reduction of 10% compared to the baseline life emissions of conventional jet fuel (ICAO, 2021a). This falls far short of the deep and fast reductions needed to meet the Paris Agreement goals. In addition, there is the inclusion of LAFs under CORSIA eligible fuels. Unlike SAFs,

which are derived from sustainable resources, LAFs are fossil-based. While less carbon-intensive than conventional jet fuel, if airlines can reduce their offsetting obligations through fossil-based fuels, the ability of CORSIA to deliver meaningful decarbonisation remains questionable.

2.2 Eligibility criteria and eligible offsetting programmes

As outlined earlier, the ICAO Council is responsible for determining which offsetting programmes and emissions units are eligible under the scheme. The Council adopted the CORSIA emissions unit eligibility criteria (EUCs) in 2019, which outline the requirements that programmes and their offset credits must fulfil to be considered eligible (ICAO, 2019d). The criteria are twofold, consisting of both 'programme design elements' and 'carbon offset integrity assessment criteria' (ICAO, 2019d). These criteria may only be amended by the ICAO Council, informed by recommendations developed by the Committee on Aviation Environmental Protection (CAEP). The CAEP, in fulfilling its role as a technical committee, is required to assist the ICAO Council in the formulation of new policies and the adoption of new SARPs. When conducting a periodic review of the EUC SARPs, the Council will also, as appropriate, promote compatibility with any future relevant decisions under Article 6 of the Paris Agreement (ICAO, 2016).

The carbon offsetting programmes and emissions units that meet the CORSIA EUCs are contained within the 'CORSIA eligible emissions units' document (ICAO, 2022a). As mentioned earlier, these are also determined by the Council upon recommendation of the TAB. In 2020, the Council completed its first decision on what EUPs to approve. As part of this decision, the Council also chose to limit vintage eligibility to units generated *pre-2020* to avoid double claiming (i.e., the claiming of one unit of emission reduction by more than one actor), as there was not yet an outcome regarding Article 6. The approved programmes from this decision include the:

- (1) American Carbon Registry (ACR);
- (2) Architecture for REDD+ Transactions (ART);
- (3) China GHG Voluntary Emissions Reduction Program (CCER);
- (4) Clean Development Mechanism (CDM);
- (5) Climate Action Reserve (CAR);
- (6) Global Carbon Council (GCC);
- (7) The Gold Standard; and
- (8) Verified Carbon Standard (VCS).

Following this initial decision, the ICAO Council has since approved two programmes to generate new credits (i.e., *post-2020* vintages) between 2021 and 2023: the ACR and ART. These programmes were approved in 2021 and can be used in the first compliance cycle of CORSIA. While the other programmes have received approval, only the ACR and ART can generate post-2020 credits. This is because they have procedures in place that avoid double claiming (ICAO, 2022a).

Some of the decisions made by the ICAO Council have been criticised. This includes the approval of the CCER. Critics have argued that this decision represents a political compromise to ensure China's involvement in CORSIA during the voluntary phases, 'rather than being based on the programme's robustness and merits' (Hitterski, 2020). The ICAO Council has also approved all CDM projects as eligible, despite the EU's decision to prohibit certain projects where environmental integrity has been considered questionable (e.g., large hydroelectric projects) (Hitterski, 2020).

2.3 Periodic review process

In accordance with Assembly Resolution A40-19, the Council is tasked with conducting a periodic review of the implementation of CORSIA – with the technical contribution of the CAEP – every three years starting in 2022 (ICAO, 2019b). These triannual reviews will provide the Council with the opportunity to improve the overall operation of the scheme and, where necessary, recommend adjustments to the next phase or compliance cycle of CORSIA (ICAO, 2019b). Specifically, Assembly Resolution A40-19 provides that the periodic review will involve, among others:

- (a) assessment of: progress towards achieving the ICAO’s global aspirational goal; the scheme’s market and cost impact on States and aeroplane operators and on international aviation; and the functioning of the scheme’s design elements;
- (b) consideration of the scheme’s improvement that would support the purpose of the Paris Agreement, in particular its long-term temperature goals; and update the scheme’s design elements to improve implementation, increase effectiveness, and minimize market distortion, taking into account the consequential impact of changing the scheme’s design elements, e.g., to [measurement, reporting and verification] requirements; and
- (c) a special review by the end of 2032 on termination of the scheme, its extension or any other improvements of the scheme beyond 2035, including consideration of the contribution made by aircraft technologies, operational improvements and sustainable aviation fuels towards achieving the ICAO’s environmental objectives (ICAO, 2019b: para. 17).

Any recommendations made by the ICAO Council on the CORSIA review will be put forward to the 41st Session of the ICAO Assembly, which is held in September 2022 and is anticipated to complete the first periodic review of the scheme (ICAO, 2022b).

3. The Paris Agreement’s Article 6 and the rulebook agreed in Glasgow

3.1 Voluntary cooperation under Articles 6.2 and 6.4

With the adoption of the Paris Agreement in 2015 and its Article 6, Parties established three possible avenues to voluntarily cooperate in the implementation of their NDCs:

- Article 6.2 allows for bilateral or multilateral ‘cooperative approaches’ to be established between Parties;
- Article 6.4 introduces a market-based mechanism that is overseen by the UNFCCC; and
- Article 6.8 allows for non-market approaches.

Article 6.2 and Article 6.4 are market-based approaches. Article 6.2 enables Parties to transfer and use emission reductions and removals as so-called internationally transferred mitigation outcomes (ITMOs). Article 6.4 creates tradable units in the form of Article 6.4 emission reductions (A6.4ERs). Both Article 6.2 and 6.4 therefore enable ITMOs or A6.4ERs respectively to be transferred from the transferring Party to the acquiring Party. Both ITMOs generated under Article 6.2 and A6.4ERs from the mechanism can be used by the acquiring Party for NDC

attainment. Since no such transfers are envisaged under Article 6.8, this type of voluntary cooperation will not be further discussed here.

The use of market-based mechanisms has proven to be controversial in the UNFCCC context. Their introduction and operationalisation proved particularly cumbersome under the Paris Agreement. At COP21 in Paris, the need to ensure a balance between proponents and opponents of market-based approaches made Article 6 the last Article to be agreed on (Howard, 2017). Therefore, it is not surprising that it took Parties almost six years to establish the rules for operationalising Article 6. The Article 6 rulebook adopted in Glasgow consists of a set of three decisions, two of which guide the operationalisation of the market-based instruments. First, Parties adopted guidance on cooperative approaches (Guidance), which can be considered a reporting and accounting framework for Article 6 (UNFCCC, 2021a). Second, for the operationalisation of the Article 6.4 mechanism, Parties adopted the rules, modalities and procedures (RMPs), which provide detailed provisions on the functioning and governance of the mechanism (UNFCCC, 2021b).

Article 6.2 can be considered an open framework that provides Parties willing to participate in cooperative approaches considerable leeway in their design and implementation. However, to make use of Article 6.2, Parties must meet some participation requirements such as having technical and institutional arrangements in place. They are also required to meet specific reporting and accounting provisions. Given the decentralised nature of Article 6.2, the reporting and transparency requirements established by the guidance are key: Parties are required to submit an initial report, annual information that is centrally recorded, as well as regular information that is included as an annex to Parties' biennial transparency reports submitted pursuant to Article 13 of the Paris Agreement. For example, under Article 6.2, Parties are required, inter alia, to provide information on their emissions balance, the transfer and use of ITMOs, and how double counting has been avoided through 'corresponding adjustments' (see Section 3.3). More generally, the accounting and reporting infrastructure of Article 6.2 is interlinked with the broader enhanced transparency framework of Article 13. Parties have also established an Article 6 review process that will be integrated into the technical expert review under Article 13 (UNFCCC, 2021a).

Building on the Article 6.2 reporting and accounting framework, Article 6.4 establishes a crediting mechanism, with detailed provisions for the implementation of creditable mitigation activities. Despite important differences, its basic structure largely resembles the functioning of the Kyoto Protocol's Clean Development Mechanism (CDM): mitigation activities must be approved by the host Party and be developed according to a methodology approved by the Supervisory Body, the entity overseeing the mechanism. Following a successful validation by a Designated Operation Entity (DOE), the activity is then registered by the Supervisory Body and its implementation is monitored by the activity participants. After successful implementation of the activity, another DOE verifies and certifies the mitigation impact achieved and submits a request for issuance to the Supervisory Body, which will then issue A6.4ERs (UNFCCC, 2021b).

3.2 The expanded scope of Article 6 and the authorisation of ITMOs and A6.4ERs

As outlined above, Article 6 was originally conceived as a tool to assist Parties in the implementation of their NDCs. With the adoption of the Article 6 rulebook, however, the scope of application was broadened. Both the Guidance and the RMPs take into account 'other international mitigation purposes' as well as 'other purposes'. Although there is no legal definition of these terms, there is wide agreement among observers that the first term ('other international mitigation purposes') refers to obligations deriving from international mitigation outside the UNFCCC, namely CORSIA. The second ('other purposes') is commonly understood as referring to the voluntary carbon market

(see e.g. Marcu, 2021). While the latter is decentralised and not subject to international regulation, the Guidance provided by the Article 6 rulebook will likely have a significant impact on the voluntary carbon market.

The application of Article 6 is thus no longer confined to NDC attainment. ITMOs and A6.4ERs may also be used outside the Paris Agreement and UNFCCC context. The Article 6 rulebook requires host Parties to decide on how ITMOs (and A6.4ERs) are to be used, by providing an authorisation for one of the three uses: (1) NDC achievement; (2) other international mitigation purposes (e.g., CORSIA); and (3) other purposes (voluntary carbon markets). The authorisation is a key step in the entire process, as it provides the host Party with the authority to define how ITMOs (and A6.4ERs) can be used. Since the authorisation of ITMOs and A6.4ERs requires host Parties to account for these mitigation outcomes, the decision on authorisation can have important repercussions on the host Party's climate policy, as will be shown in the following.

3.3 Avoidance of double claiming through corresponding adjustments

All ITMOs and authorised A6.4ERs must be robustly accounted for through 'corresponding adjustments' (CAs). The application of CAs has been proposed as a means to avoid emission reductions being claimed by more than one actor. Such double claiming is one form of double counting and is particularly problematic if emission reductions are transferred among Parties. While not an entirely new phenomenon, double claiming has not been a major concern in the past. Under the Kyoto Protocol, the largest share of carbon credits was generated by CDM activities implemented in the so-called 'uncapped environment' – i.e., in countries that had no international mitigation targets. This now changes with the Paris Agreement, which requires all Parties to adopt NDCs and to submit national inventory reports, as well as information to track progress made towards NDC achievement.

Under these circumstances, a project that is implemented in Party A would automatically reduce the Party's emissions and contribute to the achievement of its NDC. If the project is implemented as a carbon market activity, the emission reductions generated could be transferred internationally and used for NDC attainment by another Party (Party B). Without CAs, the emission reductions of the project would be claimed twice: they would appear in the inventory of Party A, while at the same time being used by Party B when reporting on its progress towards its NDC. By applying CAs, such double claiming can be avoided. While the acquiring Party B subtracts the quantity of the emission reductions from its emissions balance, the host Party (Party A) adjusts its reported emissions upwards by adding the quantity of emission reductions exported back to its emissions balance. While originally conceived as a concept to avoid emission reductions being claimed more than once if used for NDC attainment, the Article 6 rulebook expands the application of CAs to cases that only involve one Party, such as the use of ITMOs for CORSIA.

The timing of CAs is a relevant parameter for host Parties, as it may impact their ability to achieve their NDC. For mitigation outcomes that are authorised for the use against NDC attainment, CAs must be implemented when these mitigation outcomes are first transferred. For mitigation outcomes authorised to be used for other international mitigation purposes, by contrast, there is no such first transfer. Parties can therefore decide what they consider to be the first transfer, which in turn will trigger the timing of CAs. The Guidance provides three options for defining what a 'first transfer' is: (1) the authorisation; (2) the issuance; or (3) the use or cancellation of the mitigation outcome. The RMPs also require Parties to apply these rules when using the Article 6.4 mechanism for other international mitigation purposes. It will hence be up to the host Party to define when CAs will be applied. There is an incentive for the host Party to apply CAs at the latest possible moment, as the information on how these CAs will impact NDC attainment are clearer. From an environmental integrity perspective, however, it would be preferable to ensure that CAs are applied at the earliest point in time to limit the risks that non-adjusted units are

unduly used.

3.4 Accounting rules under Article 6

The adoption of the Article 6 rulebook in Glasgow has largely been hailed as a success. The adoption of the comprehensive accounting rules in particular marked one of the most significant achievements of COP26. Parties were able to agree on rules that require CAs to be applied irrespective of whether the mitigation activity is within or outside the scope of the host Party's NDC (UNFCCC, 2021a, Annex, para. 14). This means that CAs will be applicable where the mitigation outcomes originate in sectors outside the host Party's NDC. This provision in particular addresses concerns related to the perverse incentives for Parties to limit the scope of their NDC in order to evade the application of CAs. In addition, the rules further state that the 'participation in cooperative approaches does not lead to a net increase in emissions across participating Parties within and between NDC implementation periods' (UNFCCC, 2021a, Annex, para. 7), thereby also prohibiting the carry-over of units from one NDC period to the next. This prevents Parties from generating large amounts of credits not backed by actual climate action that are subsequently carried forward to achieve future climate targets (Schneider, 2021).

However, the accounting framework contains a significant loophole. This loophole relates to the bottom-up structure of the Paris Agreement, which generates a large diversity of NDCs. One parameter that differs among Parties' NDCs is their target type. NDCs may be submitted as continuous multi-year targets or as single-year targets. Multi-year targets are defined over various years, for example over the period 2021–2030. Single-year targets, on the other hand, only specify an emissions target for one future year. The latter accounts for around 85% of current NDCs (Hattori and Takahashi, 2021), which generally specify a single emissions target for the year 2030 (Schneider, 2021).

Single-year targets present major challenges for countries engaging in carbon market mechanisms under Article 6 (Siemons and Schneider, 2022). While the Article 6 rules were intended to provide important safeguards against double counting, this loophole could considerably undermine climate mitigation efforts and thus hinder the overall effectiveness of the scheme (Schneider, 2021). Parties that have submitted their NDC as a single-year target can choose between two accounting approaches: Averaging and multi-year accounting. The application of the averaging approach can effectively lead to double claiming and an increase in aggregate emissions, as shown by Siemons and Schneider (2022). Under this approach, countries with a single-year emissions target will apply CAs in their specified target year as an *average* of all units transferred (or acquired) between a certain period (e.g., 2021–2030 or 2026–2030). The application of this approach is less problematic if the ITMO engagement remains constant over time and emissions in the target year are representative of the country's emissions trend. However, Siemons and Schneider (2022) show that averaging can lead to a situation in which aggregate emissions are considerably higher and environmental integrity is undermined, in particular if ITMO generation is not constant and there is an increase in ITMO engagement of the Parties involved. In such a situation, the CAs applied by Parties might not correspond with the amount of emission reductions transferred or used.

4. Interactions between CORSIA and Article 6 rules

4.1 Accounting for single-year targets and averaging

As discussed in Section 3.4, the UNFCCC accounting rules contain one crucial loophole that could generate risks for

environmental integrity. This is particularly problematic if carbon credits are used by airline operators to offset their emissions under the CORSIA scheme, as it leads to a combination of factors that increase the risk of double claiming. For CORSIA, Siemons and Schneider (2022) expect that demand for carbon credits will increase over time, leading to a rising generation of ITMOs authorised for this purpose. The application of the averaging approach for an increasing number of ITMOs authorised for use under CORSIA is especially problematic since CORSIA specifies a multi-year approach for buying airlines. This combination of accounting approaches, averaging on the seller’s side and multi-year accounting on the buyer’s side, together with an increasing generation of ITMOs over time, could lead to considerable double claiming. Schneider (2021) shows that this may lead to a situation in which around half of the emission reductions used for compliance under CORSIA would be double claimed (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Double claiming potential under CORSIA due to averaging. Source: Schneider (2021).

As can be seen, the mismatch between single-year targets and the averaging accounting approach threatens to jeopardise the environmental integrity of Parties’ NDCs, as well as CORSIA. Where Parties’ employ single-year targets, it is thus crucial that adjustments are applied in a manner that reflects the actual use of credits over a period of time.

To ensure that the application of CAs is representative over time, it will be key that further guidance is issued on this at COP27 in Sharm El-Sheikh, Egypt. This guidance could take different forms: Parties could specify under what circumstances averaging can be applied, for instance by limiting the application of averaging to cases where the generation of ITMOs remains constant over time. This alone, however, will presumably not fully solve the issue, as the decrease or increase of ITMO generation over time is not the only aspect influencing the environmental impact of averaging. As highlighted by Siemons and Schneider (2022), the impact will also depend on the emission levels in the target year, which are only known *ex post*. One option to deal with this uncertainty would be the introduction of an ITMO buffer pool to balance out potential increases in global emissions. While holding back a sufficiently high amount of ITMOs may reduce the attractiveness of using Article 6 for the Parties involved, the introduction of a buffer pool could be seen as a pragmatic approach to accommodate the different positions in the Article 6 negotiations. Only Parties that apply the averaging approach would be required to transfer a certain share of their

ITMOs into this buffer pool. If a cooperative approach has been found to lead to an increase of global emissions, for instance following the review by the Article 6 technical expert review team, the respective amount of ITMOs would be cancelled to compensate for the climate impact incurred. Whether Parties will be open to the introduction of such an approach seems questionable, as it might increase their administrative burden. However, it would allow Parties to maintain the possibility of using the averaging approach, at least in theory, while limiting the potential adverse impacts that this approach is associated with. Ultimately, requiring Parties to transition towards multi-year targets seems the more promising way forward to ensure robust accounting.

4.2 Quality criteria for offsets

High-quality carbon credits that stimulate actual emission reductions are crucial to the overall success of CORSIA. As mentioned above, airlines may only purchase carbon credits from programmes that have received the approval of the ICAO Council (ICAO, 2019b). However, the scheme has been accused of allowing airlines to merely compensate for their emissions, opposed to actually delivering on required emissions reductions (Hodgson et al., 2021). Studies suggest that these carbon credits lack quality, bringing their effectiveness into question (Transport & Environment, 2021; Beard, 2017). A study by the NGO Transport & Environment in 2021 concluded that the initial six programmes approved in 2020 by the Council to certify offsets failed to meet all of the integrity assessment criteria (Transport & Environment, 2021). Three of the key programmes – CCER, the CDM, and the Gold Standard – failed to meet the criterion relating to additionality, meaning that the emission reductions generated by these programmes would have materialised even without existence of the carbon price incentive (Transport & Environment, 2021). There are also issues pertaining to the TAB's application of the criteria. This further calls into question whether and how environmental integrity is ensured. Rather than assessing the *actual performance* of the respective programmes against the criteria, the TAB has generally evaluated whether the programmes have necessary measures in place *to address the criteria*. In other words, the TAB does not consider whether these measures in themselves ensure carbon credit quality (Schneider and Wissner, 2022).

In this regard, the ICAO process may benefit from ongoing processes under the Article 6.4 mechanism. The RMPs adopted in Glasgow establish some fundamental requirements that methodologies under the Article 6.4 mechanism must meet in order to be approved by the Supervisory Body. Some of these requirements go well beyond existing approaches, for instance under the CDM. In terms of baseline setting, for instance, the rules require baseline methodologies to apply approaches based on performance, such as best available technologies to ensure that baselines are below 'business as usual' and 'align to the long-term temperature goal of the Paris Agreement' (UNFCCC, 2021b, Annex, paras. 36 and 33). By the same token, additionality must be demonstrated by 'taking into account all relevant national policies, including legislation, and representing mitigation that exceeds any mitigation that is required by law or regulation' (UNFCCC, 2021b, Annex, para. 38). While it remains to be seen how the Supervisory Body will put these rules into practice, voluntary certification standards are already considering how to align their rules with these requirements (Kreibich and Brandemann, 2022).

Instead of waiting for these more ambitious rules to spill over into certification schemes outside the UNFCCC, the ICAO Council could take on a more active role by phasing in the ambitious requirements of the Article 6.4 mechanism into its own assessment processes. In doing so, the overall quality of credits eligible under CORSIA could be increased. In addition, it is worth noting that there are several initiatives that independently assess and distinguish the quality of carbon credits. Examples include the Carbon Credit Quality Initiative, Calyx Global and the Integrity Council for the Voluntary Carbon Market. It is possible that these initiatives emerged in response to ICAO's

failure to identify high-quality carbon credits. Importantly, some have published their methodologies. To ensure the quality of credits under CORSIA, ICAO could therefore draw from these independent initiatives.

4.3 Level of ambition in ICAO decision-making

With the adoption of the Article 6 rulebook at COP26 in Glasgow, the links between CORSIA and Article 6 have been tightened. Policymakers at ICAO should be aware of this and consider that their policy decisions may have a wider impact on the supply side of the CORSIA market, namely the voluntary carbon market and Article 6.4; both linked to the Article 6.2 accounting and reporting framework. In the past, however, decision-making by ICAO has been characterised by a lack of ambition.

One example is the modification of CORSIA's baseline in light of the COVID-19 pandemic. The pandemic resulted in a dramatic decline of CO₂ emissions from international aviation. In response to this, the ICAO Council modified the baseline for the pilot phase (ICAO, 2020). Rather than using the average of 2019 and 2020 CO₂ emissions from international flights, the baseline was revised to 2019 emissions only. It is anticipated that this will increase the baseline by roughly 30%, translating into fewer offsetting obligations (Harper, 2020). According to Schneider and Graichen (2020), this adjustment could give rise to a complete elimination of all offsetting requirements during the pilot phase, resulting in a delay of the scheme's implementation by three to five years (Harper, 2020). The ICAO Assembly is yet to formally adopt this decision at the 41st Assembly Session in 2022, however. In March 2022, CAEP's analysis in support of CORSIA's periodic review was presented to the ICAO Council 225th Session. This analysis also shows that a 2019 baseline would significantly reduce offsetting requirements under the scheme (ICAO, 2022c).

Another example concerns the impact of non-CO₂ effects on the climate. Non-CO₂ effects from aviation, including the effects of nitrogen oxide, sulphate aerosols and contrails, for example, have a significant influence on climate change (Beard, 2017). CO₂ emissions only account for a small portion of overall aviation emissions. A scientific study published in 2021 concluded that the total climate impact of the aviation sector is actually three times greater than the impact of all CO₂ emissions alone (Lee et al., 2021). Accordingly, the regulation of non-CO₂ impacts will be crucial in realising the objectives of the Paris Agreement. However, CORSIA currently only targets CO₂ emissions from international flights. Hence, it only regulates around half of the global warming impact of international aviation (Beard, 2017). Schneider and Wissner (2022) put forward some practical recommendations to this end, including the establishment of a monitoring system for non-CO₂ effects, the adoption of policies to reduce non-CO₂ effects such as re-routing, and requiring that any residual non-CO₂ effects are offset after 2030.

To generate high-quality credits that can be used by airlines under CORSIA, planning security is key for activity proponents, governments and other stakeholders. This must be seen in the context of the new framework conditions brought about by the Paris Agreement. These require a much more active involvement of host Party governments when it comes to identifying mitigation activities that can generate credits authorised by host Parties. By increasing the ambition of CORSIA, the ICAO Council would send a clear message to the supply side that demand will continue to grow in the future. Host Parties would be reassured that developing an Article 6 strategy is worthwhile, while other stakeholders would be incentivised to engage in this process to generate the offset credits needed to meet future demands.

4.4 Registries

The linkages between Article 6 and CORSIA will also become stronger at the technical level. One area where the

UNFCCC negotiations are influenced by the CORSIA structure is the development of the infrastructure of Article 6, in particular the registries to be used under Article 6. The Article 6.2 Guidance requires participating Parties to have or have access to a registry that tracks units and ITMOs and that records authorisations, transfers and uses against NDCs among others (UNFCCC, 2021a, Annex, paras 29-31). While most Parties argue that only national and international registries should be allowed to meet this requirement, Canada, Singapore, and the United States also want to make registries from private certification standards eligible (Michaelowa, 2022), following the structure introduced by CORSIA.

However, the structure of private certification standards' registries is still very diverse and lacks consistency. Exclusively relying on these registries for international transfers is therefore not desirable. At the same time, private certification standards need to operate their own registries, for instance to show compliance with upcoming requirements from initiatives such as the Integrity Council for the Voluntary Carbon Market (IC-VCM, 2022). A possible way forward would be to link national and international registries with the registries from private certification standards. While the former would track units and record uses, the latter would basically function as databases for the purpose of transparency.

5. Managing the interplay between CORSIA and Article 6

As the previous section shows, while CORSIA was developed and adopted outside the UNFCCC, there are clear links to the international climate regime, in particular its new mechanisms developed under Article 6 of the Paris Agreement. The adoption of the Article 6 rulebook in Glasgow forms a new chapter in the longer-standing saga of interactions between the two international regimes. However, while it may be clear that ICAO is the primary international body dealing with aviation emissions, it is much less clear what happens in case of a conflict with the goals, principles, or rules of the international climate regime. This raises the question of how interplay between rule development under ICAO and the UNFCCC/Paris Agreement can and should be managed (see generally Martinez Romera, 2018).

In this regard, several ICAO Assembly Resolutions explicitly acknowledge cooperation with the UNFCCC. For example, Resolution A40-19 refers to 'welcoming' cooperation between ICAO and the UNFCCC with regard to the development of CDM methodologies concerning aviation (ICAO, 2019b: preamble). A further example is Resolution A40-18, which requests the ICAO Council to continue cooperating with relevant organisations, with specific mention of the Conference of the Parties to the UNFCCC (ICAO, 2019e: para. 2(c)). The Resolution also asks the Council to request ICAO Member States 'to regularly report CO₂ emissions from international aviation to the UNFCCC' (ICAO, 2019e: para. 15).

ICAO regularly submits inputs into the UNFCCC process, through formal submissions and statements to the UNFCCC's Subsidiary Body for Scientific and Technological Advice (SBSTA). For instance, in a submission made to the SBSTA, ICAO set out the progress made by ICAO and its Member States since the previous Assembly in 2019, including on CORSIA (ICAO, 2021b). As well as reporting on CORSIA related milestones and future areas of work, the statement also acknowledged that ICAO would 'continue to monitor further developments related to Article 6 of the Paris Agreement, in particular, any implications for the implementation of CORSIA and its eligible emissions units' (ICAO, 2021b: 1).

The question is whether such reporting and monitoring on the part of ICAO is sufficient to address the concerns

raised in Section 4. While CORSIA and the Paris rulebook will continue to be elaborated through separate intergovernmental processes, it will be important that ICAO and the UNFCCC strengthen cooperation with a view to aligning their efforts and avoiding the creation of rules that may hamper the environmental integrity and broader functioning of each mechanism.

The CORSIA review process should play a role in this regard. The review process specifically involves consideration of the scheme's improvement to 'support the purpose of the Paris Agreement' (ICAO, 2019b: 6). To this end, ICAO should continue to pursue Paris-compatibility as part of its review process and in parallel with ongoing COP negotiations. The first opportunity to do so will be when the ICAO Council puts forward suggestions for updating Resolution A40-19 at the next ICAO Assembly in September 2022. The ways in which ICAO Member States could ensure compatibility with the Paris Agreement in general, and Article 6 in particular, would be to request the ICAO Council to carry out an assessment of the impacts on the functioning of the Article 6 mechanisms each time a decision is made. Moreover, to address the issue of the quality of offsets, the Council could be requested to align its guidance with that of the Article 6.4 Supervisory Body.

From the perspective of the Paris Agreement, the Glasgow Climate Conference delivered the bulk of the rulebook on Article 6. Still, at COP27, Parties will have to clarify some of the outstanding issues, in particular, related to the operationalisation of the Article 6.4 mechanism, such as national arrangements for the mechanism, processes for the transition of CDM activities to the Article 6.4 mechanism, and operation of the mechanism registry (UNFCCC, 2021b, para 7). With regard to Article 6.2, Parties will have to agree on reporting tables and outlines as well as on infrastructure needed for tracking and recording of ITMOs (UNFCCC, 2021b: paras 6 and 10). One aspect on the agenda that is of particular relevance to CORSIA is the elaboration of further guidance in relation to the avoidance of double claiming and the application of CAs to single-year targets, including through averaging (UNFCCC, 2021a, Annex, para 3).

6. Conclusions and recommendations

The adoption of the Article 6 rulebook marked a significant step forward for the continued evolution of carbon markets. The rules adopted under Article 6 of the Paris Agreement provide a strong framework for Parties to pursue voluntary cooperation and realise the emission reduction targets specified in their NDCs. While originally intended to support Parties in the implementation of their NDCs, however, the expanded scope of Article 6 has also created a direct linkage to CORSIA. This paper has sought to explore this linkage, in particular, by analysing four key interactions between the Article 6 rules and CORSIA: (1) the use of single-year targets and the averaging accounting approach; (2) quality criteria for offsets; (3) unpredictability in ICAO decision-making; and (4) the use of registries. To this end, the paper has offered some possible suggestions on how to address the challenges associated with these interactions.

While CORSIA and Article 6 are elaborated through separate regimes, the future development of these systems, and in particular the extent to which they align, has important implications for their overall effectiveness in achieving global emission reductions. The future interplay between ICAO and the UNFCCC will thus be crucial in unlocking the full potential of international emissions trading. This paper has shown, however, that the current regulations contain some severe loopholes that could significantly undermine the environmental integrity of CORSIA and Article 6. The first move is for ICAO Member States, which are to complete the first review of CORSIA

at the 41st ICAO Assembly in September 2022. This provides an important opportunity to consider CORSIA's alignment with the Paris Agreement and its implementing rules. More generally, ICAO Member States should consider the impacts of their decision-making on the Article 6 mechanisms.

In particular, ICAO Member States should adopt a long-term climate target for international aviation in line with the Paris Agreement. It will be vital that CORSIA's current objective is also revised to align with such a long-term goal. This would be particularly important in addressing the currently limited focus of CORSIA on emissions *growth* rather than actual emissions *reduction*. Additionally, ICAO should also revise its quality criteria for offsets if it is to ensure the overall effectiveness of the scheme. In particular, the ICAO Council should seek to enhance the quality of credits eligible under CORSIA by integrating the more ambitious requirements under the Article 6.4 mechanism. A further element for consideration by ICAO is the regulation of non-CO₂ effects from international aviation. Finally, ICAO should consider carrying out an assessment of the impacts on the functioning of the Article 6 mechanisms each time a decision is made.

While COP26 laid the foundation for the operationalisation of Article 6, some outstanding issues will have to be agreed on, including at this year's COP27 in November. Addressing the concerns related to double claiming in the context of averaging will be relevant for ensuring the integrity of both CORSIA and Parties' NDCs. In particular, the guidance on averaging should be further refined or a decision on the establishment of a buffer tool should be considered. In the long run, however, requiring all Parties to transition towards multi-year targets seems most promising. Agreeing on this from the start will presumably be challenging, if not impossible, given the bottom-up structure of the Paris Agreement. Therefore, restricting the application of averaging and introducing safeguards could ultimately prove to be more realistic. If this alternative path is chosen, ensuring environmental integrity should always be a priority. While potentially challenging, CORSIA should also consider accepting only units from host Parties with multi-year emission budgets. In addition to addressing the issues concerning double claiming and the averaging approach, the registry issue should also be resolved. One possible avenue forward would involve linking national and international registries with the registries from private certification standards.

Addressing these challenges and ultimately closing the loopholes identified in this paper will be crucial in ensuring the environmental integrity and wider functioning of CORSIA and Article 6. Accordingly, it will be vitally important that ICAO and the UNFCCC pursue strong cooperation to ensure that their efforts are aligned and can sufficiently address the concerns raised in this paper.

References

- Beard, J. (2017). Grounded: Tens reasons why international offsetting won't solve Heathrow's climate change problem. WWF. https://www.wwf.org.uk/sites/default/files/2017-05/WWF_Grounded_report_FINAL_1.pdf.
- Chiaromonti, D., Talluri, G., Vourliotakis, G., Testa, L., Prussi, M., & Scarlat, N. (2021). Can Lower Carbon Aviation Fuels (LCAF) Really Complement Sustainable Aviation Fuel (SAF) Towards EU Aviation Decarbonization? *Energies*, 14(19), 6430-6458. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14196430>.
- Hattori, T., & Takahashi, K. (2021). IGES NDC Database. Institute for Global Environmental Strategies. <https://www.iges.or.jp/en/pub/iges-indc-ndc-database/en>.
- Hiterski, K. (2020). CORSIA Offset Eligibility Explainer. Redshaw Advisors Ltd. <https://redshawadvisors.com/corsia-offset-eligibility-explainer/>.

Hodgson, C., Georgiadis, P., Hook, L., & Khan, M. (2021). Aviation industry carbon scheme highly flawed, Brussels warned. *Climate Capital*, Financial Times. <https://www.ft.com/content/296121c6-1af5-4ef4-b674-c3389b6de33c#comments-anchor/>.

Howard, A. (2017). Voluntary Cooperation (Article 6). In D. R. Klein, M. P. Carazo, M. Doelle, J. Bulmer, & A. Higham (Eds.), *The Paris Agreement on Climate change: Analysis and Commentary* (pp. 178–195). Oxford University Press.

IATA. (2019). CORSIA Takes Center Stage. IATA. <https://www.airlines.iata.org/analysis/corsia-takes-center-stage>.

ICAO. (2010). Resolution A37-19: Consolidated statement of continuing ICAO policies and practices related to environmental protection – Climate change. https://www.icao.int/environmental-protection/37thAssembly/A37_Res19_en.pdf

ICAO. (2016). Resolution A39-3: Consolidated statement of continuing ICAO policies and practices related to environmental protection – Global Market-based Measure (MBM) scheme. https://www.icao.int/environmental-protection/documents/resolution_a39_3.pdf/.

ICAO. (2018). COUNCIL - First Edition of Annex 16 – Environmental Protection, Volume IV – Carbon Offsetting Reduction Scheme for International Aviation. <https://www.icao.int/environmental-protection/CORSIA/Pages/SARPs-Annex-16-Volume-IV.aspx>.

ICAO. (2019a). Destination Green. The Next Chapter. ICAO 2019 Environmental Report. [https://www.icao.int/environmental-protection/Documents/ICAO-ENV-Report2019-F1-WEB%20\(1\).pdf](https://www.icao.int/environmental-protection/Documents/ICAO-ENV-Report2019-F1-WEB%20(1).pdf).

ICAO. (2019b). Resolution A40-19: Consolidated statement of continuing ICAO policies and practices related to environmental protection – Carbon Offsetting and Reduction Scheme for International Aviation (CORSIA). https://www.icao.int/environmental-protection/Documents/Assembly/Resolution_A40-19_CORSIA.pdf.

ICAO. (2019c). Terms of Reference (TOR) for the Technical Advisory Body (TAB). <https://www.icao.int/environmental-protection/CORSIA/Documents/TAB/TOR%20of%20TAB.pdf>.

ICAO. (2019d). CORSIA Emissions Unit Eligibility Criteria. https://www.icao.int/environmental-protection/CORSIA/Documents/ICAO_Document_09.pdf.

ICAO. (2019e). Resolution A40-18: Consolidated statement of continuing policies and practices related to environmental protection – Climate change. https://www.icao.int/environmental-protection/Documents/Assembly/Resolution_A40-18_Climate_Change.pdf.

ICAO. (2021a). CORSIA Sustainability Criteria for CORSIA Eligible Fuels. <https://www.icao.int/environmental-protection/CORSIA/Documents/ICAO%20document%2005%20-%20Sustainability%20Criteria%20-%20November%202021.pdf>.

ICAO. (2021b). Submission by the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) The second part of the 2021 session of the UNFCCC Subsidiary Body for Scientific and Technological Advice (SBSTA 52-55) Glasgow, United Kingdom – 31 October to 6 November 2021 Agenda item 12 (g). Methodological issues under the Convention: Emissions from fuel used for international aviation and maritime transport. https://www.icao.int/environmental-protection/Documents/SBSTA2021_ICAO%20submission_Final.pdf.

ICAO. (2022a). CORSIA Eligible Emissions Units. https://www.icao.int/environmental-protection/CORSIA/Documents/TAB/ICAO%20Document%2008_CORSIA%20Eligible%20Emissions%20Units_March%202022.pdf.

ICAO. (2022b). Council – 225th Council. C-DEC 225/13. Input by the Committee on Aviation Environmental Protection (CAEP) to the 2022 CORSIA Periodic Review (March, 2022). <https://www.icao.int/about-icao/Council/Council%20Documentation/225/C-DEC/C.225.DEC.13.EN.PDF>.

ICAO. (2022c). CAEP Inputs to the 225th Session of the ICAO Council on the 2022 Corsia Periodic Review. Executive Summary. https://www.icao.int/environmental-protection/CORSIA/Documents/CAEP_CORSIA%20Periodic%20Review%20%28C225%29_Executive%20Summary.pdf.

ICSA. (2018). ICSA Views on a Long-term Climate Goal for International Aviation. ICSA. <http://www.icsa-aviation.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/ICSA-views-LTG-June-2018.pdf>.

IC-VCM. (2022). The Integrity Council for Voluntary Carbon Markets: Transparency for Voluntary Carbon Markets, Offsets & Credits. ICVCM. <https://icvcm.org/>.

IEA. (2020). Tracking Aviation 2020. Tracking Report. IEA. <https://www.iea.org/reports/tracking-aviation-2020>.

- Kreibich, N., Brandemann, V., (2022). From Glasgow to the future: How does the COP26 outcome shape tomorrow's voluntary carbon market. Carbon Mechanisms Research Policy Paper 02/2022. Wuppertal Institut für Klima, Umwelt, Energie. www.carbon-mechanisms.de/VCM_Glasgow
- Lee, D.S., Fahey, D.W., Skowron, A., Allen, M.R., Burkhardt, U., Chen, Q., Doherty, S.J., Freeman, S., Forster, P.M., Fuglestedt, J., Gettelman, A., De León R.R., Lim, L.L., Lund, M.T., Millar, R.J., Owen, B., Penner, J.E., Pitari, G., Prather, M.J., Sausen, R., Wilcox, L.J. (2021). The contribution of global aviation to anthropogenic climate forcing for 2000 to 2018. *Atmospheric Environment*, 244, 117834-1178362. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2020.117834>.
- Marcu, A. (2021). Article 6 rule book—A post COP26 assessment. 13. <https://ercst.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/20211122-COP26-Art6-final.pdf>.
- Martinez Romera, B. (2016). The Paris Agreement and the regulation of international bunker fuels. *Review of European, Comparative and International Environmental Law*, 25(2), 215–227. <https://doi.org/10.1111/reel.12170>.
- Martinez Romera, B. (2018). *Regime Interaction and Climate Change: The Case of International Aviation and Maritime Transport*. Routledge.
- Michaelowa, A. (2022). Crunch issues in Article 6 negotiations. SB 56 Ringo Meeting. <https://ringosnet.wordpress.com/sb-56/>.
- Murphy, A. (2020). Inclusion of international aviation emissions under the Paris Agreement's Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs). In F. Fichert, P. Forsyth, H. Niemeier, *Aviation and Climate Change: Economic Perspectives on Greenhouse Gas Reduction Policies*. Routledge.
- Overton, J. (2022). Issue Brief | The Growth in Greenhouse Gas Emissions from Commercial Aviation (2019, revised 2022). Environmental and Energy Study Institute. <https://www.eesi.org/papers/view/fact-sheet-the-growth-in-greenhouse-gas-emissions-from-commercial-aviation>
- Pidcock, R., & Yeo, S. (2016). Analysis: Aviation could consume a quarter of 1.5C carbon budget by 2050. *Carbon Brief*. <https://www.carbonbrief.org/aviation-consume-quarter-carbon-budget>.
- Schneider, L. (2021, November 15). #COP26 in Glasgow delivered rules for international carbon markets – how good or bad are they?. Öko-Institut e.V.: Blog. <https://blog.oeko.de/glasgow-delivered-rules-for-international-carbon-markets-how-good-or-bad-are-they-cop26/>.
- Schneider, L., & Graichen, J. (2020). Should CORSIA be changed due to the COVID-19 crisis? Öko-Institut. <https://www.oeko.de/fileadmin/oekodoc/Should-CORSIA-be-changed-due-to-the-COVID-19-crisis.pdf>
- Schneider, L., & Wissner, N. (2022). Fit for purpose? Key issues for the review of CORSIA. Öko-Institut. <https://www.oeko.de/fileadmin/oekodoc/Key-issues-for-first-review-of-CORSIA.pdf>.
- Siemons, A., & Schneider, L. (2022). Averaging or multi-year accounting? Environmental integrity implications for using international carbon markets in the context of single-year targets. *Climate Policy*, 22(2), 208–221. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2021.2013154>.
- Transport & Environment. (2021). CORSIA: Worst Option for the Climate. Briefing Assessment of ICAO's Offsetting Scheme. T&E. https://www.transportenvironment.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/2021_03_Briefing_Corsia_EU_assesment_2021.pdf.
- UNFCCC. (2021a). Decision 2/CMA.3, Guidance on cooperative approaches referred to in Article 6, paragraph 2, of the Paris Agreement. UN Doc. FCCC/PA/CMA/2021/10/Add.1. United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change.
- UNFCCC. (2021b). Decision 3/CMA.3, Rules, modalities and procedures for the mechanism established by Article 6, paragraph 4, of the Paris Agreement. UN Doc. FCCC/PA/CMA/2021/10/Add.1. United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change.

NDC ASPECTS

POLICY BRIEF

Article 6 and CORSIA after
Glasgow: Ready for take-off?

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NDC ASPECTS

Submission

**Ensuring an Effective Global Stocktake
with a Sectoral Perspective**

August 2022

Submission by the Wuppertal Institute
on behalf of the NDC ASPECTS Project

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Executive Summary

A sectoral perspective can help the Global Stocktake (GST) to effectively achieve its objective to inform Parties' in enhancing subsequent NDCs and in enhancing international cooperation. Specifically, granular and actionable sectoral lessons, grounded in country-driven assessments, should be identified and elaborated. To be effective, conversations on sectoral transformations need to synthesise key challenges and opportunities identified in the national analyses and link them to international enablers; focus on systemic interdependencies, involve diverse actors, and be thoroughly prepared including by pre-scoping points of convergences and divergence across transformations. We specifically recommend that:

- the co-facilitators of the Technical Dialogue use their (limited) mandate to facilitate an effective conversation on sectoral transformations e.g. by organising dedicated informal seminars in between formal negotiation sessions;
- key systemic transformations necessary to achieve net-zero by mid-century should be spelled out and included in the final decision or political declaration of the GST; and
- the political outcome of the GST should mandate follow-up processes at the regional level and encourage national-level conversations to translate the collective messages from GST into actionable and sector-specific policy recommendations.

Moreover, the GST can further support NDC enhancement by endorsing key scientific benchmarks for achieving the 1.5°C goal of the Paris Agreement. These benchmarks can then be employed by stakeholders as an indicative yardstick to assess draft NDCs before adoption. Building on our own analysis of global model results, we propose key benchmarks in selected sectors (see table).

Sector	Indicator	Benchmark
Power	Share of coal in power generation	Near zero by 2030 in developed and 2040 in developing countries.
	CO ₂ emissions per unit of electricity	150 grCO ₂ /kWh in 2030, and zero ideally before 2050.
	Share of renewables in electricity generation	50% in 2030 and at least 70-80% in 2050.
Industry	Global CO ₂ emissions from industry	-27% by 2030 and -70% by 2050 relative to 2010.
	Share of electricity in industrial energy consumption	30% in 2030 and at least 50% in 2050.
Transport	Global transport CO ₂ emissions	Stabilise at current levels through 2030 and decline to -50% by 2050 relative to 2010.
	Share of electricity in total transport energy consumption	5% in 2030 and further and up to 15-30% by 2050.
	Share of non-fossil fuels in domestic-only transport energy consumption	90-100% by 2050.
Buildings	Global CO ₂ emissions from buildings	-25% by 2030 and -70% in 2050 relative to 2010.
	Share of electricity in buildings' energy consumption	45% in 2030 and 65-70% in 2050.
AFOLU	land required per year for net afforestation	~2 million ha annually between 2030 and 2050.

Likewise, a sectoral perspective included in the GST may inform enhanced international cooperation by closing important governance gaps. Specifically, we recommend that

- Parties should voluntarily report on sectoral transformation challenges, including economic, financial, technical, political/institutional and capacity-related barriers. The modalities, procedures and guidelines to the Enhanced Transparency Framework should be revised at the next occasion to include a mandate to do so.
- the outputs of the GST should identify and summarise key opportunities for sectoral climate governance sector by sector and call on other international organisations to exploit the identified opportunities as appropriate.
- Parties to the Paris Agreement use the GST to send a signal to other intergovernmental institutions, including the ICAO and IMO, requesting periodic reports in which these institutions indicate not only what measures have been adopted, but also how those measures are aligned with the Paris Agreement's long-term goals.

Introduction

Achieving the objectives of the Paris Agreement requires a fundamental transformation of global societies and economies (IPCC, 2022) and focusing on effective and coordinated action. Our economies are underpinned by a patchwork of interrelated and interdependent sectoral systems, each supplying distinct goods and services such as energy, transport and mobility, agricultural products and food, residential and commercial buildings, or industrial products. Sectoral transformations are urgently needed and will involve changes in institutions, infrastructure, markets, business models, and social customs. Each sectoral system is distinct in its political economy, technologies, financing structures and industrial composition, and the nature and extent of its international connectedness. Each sectoral system requires its own transformation, and barriers to, and opportunities for transformation vary strongly from sector to sector.

To be effective, climate policy therefore needs to recognise and address sectoral specificities (Oberthür et al., 2021; Rayner et al., 2021; Victor et al., 2019), and take into consideration the interlinkages between sectors. Sectoral perspectives allow us to connect the national to the global level by recognising the systemic interrelations across national borders. It highlights the imperative and the potential of international cooperation on climate change mitigation, which will fail without adequate institutional capacity at all levels (IPCC, 2022). The application of sectoral lenses facilitates the understanding of individual countries' contributions to global transformation in each of the sectoral systems while exposing local actors to the differences that arise from national versus global perspectives on a sector-specific decarbonisation strategies (Torres Gunfaus & Waisman, 2021). Ultimately, successful implementation of climate policies must inevitably address and enable sectoral transformations occurring at the national level.

What is a "sectoral system"?

Sectoral systems provide identifiable societal functions such as transport, electricity, or raw materials for industrial production. They are constituted of ensembles of actors (corporations, administrative bodies, political groups/parties, international organisations), technologies and infrastructures, economic structures, institutions and ideas that produce degrees of path dependency and resistance to change. Sectoral systems are complex in the sense that they (1) produce emergent phenomena/effects that are more than the sum of the systems' parts, and (2) they are open, i.e. closely related to and potentially overlapping and interdependent with other sectoral systems.

Source: Oberthür et al. (2021).

In the run-up to and during the first technical dialogue (TD) of the Global Stocktake (GST) many Parties and observers pointed to the need for a sectoral perspective.¹ However, to date, the UNFCCC has been ill-equipped to introduce sectoral perspectives. Historically, negotiations under the UNFCCC were not held along sectoral lines, with very few exceptions² that have had only limited impact in moving forward sector transformations. Moreover, the GST modalities adopted at COP24 in Katowice provide only very limited time and no explicit mandate for sectoral discussions. Notwithstanding these constraints, sectoral approaches grounded in country-driven assessments could be key to maximizing the GST's efficacy with respect to informing national action while enhancing international cooperation. In the margins of the multilateral negotiations by countries sector-oriented pledges are emerging supported by multiple actors (governments, business, etc.), showing the importance of sectoral perspectives.

¹ See for instance [submission by Switzerland on behalf of the Environmental Integrity Group](#) (dated 13 April 2022).

² For example, the negotiations of issues related to REDD+ and the Koronivia Joint Work on Agriculture.

With a focus on mitigation, this submission highlights ways in which addressing bottom-up and sector-specific transformation challenges can help GST discussions to progress within the limitations of its mandate. According to Article 14.3 of the Paris Agreement, the GST has a dual mandate to inform Parties (1) in enhancing and updating their national actions and support and (2) in enhancing international cooperation. This submission is structured accordingly, first highlighting the ways in which the GST might effectively link to national level policy processes towards developing and adopting NDCs and, second, highlighting gaps in the existing global climate governance landscape and suggesting ways that the GST may contribute to closing those gaps with a sectoral perspective.

In doing so, this submission responds to the following overarching questions:

- What information is required (ICP guiding question 6) and what action needs to be taken to overcome barriers and challenges to transformations to ultimately enhance ambition (TA guiding question 5)?
- Which opportunities exist to enhance international cooperation and governance to create an enabling international environment for deep transformations (ICP guiding question 32; TA guiding question 22)?
- What is the role of diverse actors for the transformation of key sectoral systems (related to TA guiding question 21)?

Enhancing National Ambition in Subsequent NDCs

The GST is a central cog in the ambition cycle of the Paris Agreement. It establishes a feedback loop connecting the national-level implementation of NDCs with the overarching global long-term goals of the Paris Agreement with a view to influencing and inspiring national agendas towards more ambitious subsequent NDCs and enhancing international cooperation. In the logic of a results change framework, the immediate outputs of the GST are supposed to lead to informed policy processes towards new NDCs at the national level. The intended impact of this logic is that these policy processes result in enhanced ambition. But how can this be best achieved? How can we support the actual unfolding of this logical chain?

AGENDA SETTING: What can be done to improve the immediate reception of the GST results on the national level to frame the political and media agenda?

POLICY FORMULATION: How do the results of the GST be presented to facilitate the formulation of concrete policies?

DECISION MAKING: How can the outputs of the GST enable the assessment of initial policy proposals before the final adoption of the NDC?

Figure 1 How can the GST influence the NDC policy cycle at the nation level?
Source: adapted from Hermwille et al. (2019)

We argue that the GST can influence the national NDC policy process at three distinct stages: agenda setting, policy formulation and decision making (Figure 1). For the agenda-setting phase, the political profile of the GST is particularly important. Participation at the heads-of-state level will raise public attention and increase the chances that stakeholders at the national and sectoral level can use the international event as a fulcrum to leverage political discourse towards the development of a more ambitious NDC also at the national level. In the following, we will develop specific recommendations on how the outputs of the GST should be designed to effectively resonate with the NDC process at the national level with a special focus on the policy formulation and decision-making phases.

Informing policy formulation for NDCs

It has been argued that the GST may become a platform for transformational learning requiring not only factual learning through the aggregation and assessment of new data but also collective meaning making related to those data in the light of national experiences and changing values (Milkoreit & Haapala, 2018). To be effective in this regard, the right lessons need to be identified and they need to be processed in a way so that they are actually learnt, i.e. picked up and adequately reflected in actual behavioural change, notably by way of inclusion in subsequent NDCs. Again, we argue that a sectoral perspective can facilitate this process by providing necessary granularity and practical and actionable detail.

The GST's mandate and modalities do not provide an explicit space for focused conversations on specific sectoral systems and their respective transformation challenges. However, the chairs of the TD have some leeway in designing the process. During the first session of the TD the formal roundtables were less effective in leveraging a genuine dialogue. Parties often repeated well-known negotiation positions and their broad thematic scope was not conducive to enabling a focused discussion of specific transformation drivers and barriers. Instead, the world café event was more effective in this regard. **We recommend that the co-facilitators of the TD use their (limited) mandate to facilitate an effective conversation on sectoral transformations e.g. by organising dedicated informal seminars in between formal negotiation sessions. These seminars should focus on specific sectoral transformation challenges such as for instance the challenges for decarbonising freight transport, access to and cost of international capital for renewable energy deployment, or the decarbonisation of primary iron- and steelmaking.**

Moreover, the material collected during the ICP phase and the first technical dialogues should already suffice to identify selected key systemic transformations and their international enablers. Building on the sector-specific seminars proposed above, it should be possible to **spell out those key systemic transformations necessary to achieve net-zero by mid-century for inclusion in the final decision or political declaration of the GST. These transformations should be grounded in the latest science, and be able to speak directly to real world actors, in a way that they can send a signal to speed up the transition.**

Due to the limitations of its mandate, we cannot assume that the GST will address sectoral transformations at sufficient level of detail. Moreover, global trends need to be revisited in the light of national and regional circumstances to be effectively picked-up in policy formulation. **We therefore recommend that the political outcome of the GST should mandate follow-up processes at the regional level and encourage national level conversations to translate the collective messages from GST into actionable and sector-specific policy recommendations. This follow-up should build on and further elaborate the global climate action pathways developed under auspices of high-level champions and draw on the existing regional climate weeks as appropriate and hold similar events in regions that are not yet covered.**

Conditions for successful conversations on sectoral transformations

Taking advantage of experiences made during the sectoral conversations of the NDC ASPECTS research project we have identified four key conditions for success in advancing effective conversations.

Synthesise key challenges and opportunities identified in the national analyses and link them to international enablers: Obviously, the specific circumstances vary substantially between countries. While not all differences can be adequately addressed, information on the socio-economic and distributional effects of the transformations and on the barriers to the scale up of action, given the key challenges and opportunities identified in the national analyses is key (Fazekas et al., 2022). From this, global conditions can be distilled that could help overcome the barriers and support increases in climate ambition and can also guide priorities of international cooperation. The GST represents a unique opportunity to discuss these international enablers of national transformations towards net zero.

Focus on systemic interdependencies: Most current national mitigation strategies are focusing efforts on technological aspects of decarbonisation transitions. While these are necessary, they will suffice to reach global carbon neutrality. The scientific community already warned that many other options, such as demand-side solutions, should be taken into account (IPCC, 2022); and that technological change could not be seriously implemented without taking into account the overall societal transformations in which it should take place (IPCC, 2018b). Misconceptions still exist on the nature of national and systemic transformations required by global carbon neutrality. For example, in the transport sector, the focus is often given to technological energy efficiency measures (SLOCAT, 2021) or the change of vehicle motorisation and fuel supply, which are not sufficient at all to reach carbon neutrality. For instance, in freight transfer, the transformations of the production and consumptions systems need to be considered to unlock the full mitigation potential (Briand & Waisman, 2019). To be effective, conversations on sectoral transformations need to embrace those wider systemic interdependencies.

Involve diverse actors: Current international climate dialogues often focus on public policy perspectives and have difficulties in offering a fair and equal representation to national challenges in the Global North and South (Beuermann et al., 2021). However, system transitions for global carbon neutrality require by definition the coordination of multiple decisions taken by countries, but also by non-state actors, regions, cities, companies, and citizens, and so on, in different but interconnected worldwide regions (IPCC, 2022). Discussing a specific transformation and related enablers, therefore, requires gathering the relevant participants who could share specific domestic perspectives on implementation challenges and those who could act on the specific enablers. Representing scientific perspectives from the Global South alongside the hitherto dominant Northern voices may close important gaps and broaden the scientific evidence base for the conversations.

Thoroughly prepare conversations: Aside from the relevant actors for the discussion, it is crucial to develop a strategy for the conversation, playing on the positions of different actors and relations among them, to help catalyse reactions, reveal threats and opportunities, and prepare the ground for effective and constructive dialogues around trade-offs embedded in different courses of actions and policy solutions that navigate the trade-offs while maximising synergies and benefits to actors involved. For that, the work of experienced facilitators is key: they should be nominated at least a month in advance of each conversation, and be required to coordinate with key participants beforehand to be able to extract the most of the discussions. This pre-dialogue scoping could notably identify points of convergences and key points of divergence across transformations, so that the TDs can crystallise the former and allow progress on the latter through a facilitated and well-prepared exchange.

Supporting decision making towards adopting ambitious NDCs

The GST needs to provide clear benchmarks at the sectoral level that national-level stakeholders can employ as a yardstick to gauge the adequacy and ambition of their government's (draft) NDCs. The adoption of a new NDC is a highly political process. Our research shows that transparent and open participatory processes in the development of NDCs as well as a high level of democratically legitimised scrutiny is a key determinant of high NDC ambition (Peterson et al., forthcoming). The question is, how can this kind of involvement of stakeholders and civil society more broadly be facilitated effectively? Much like the 1.5°C temperature goal has empowered civil society actors such as the Fridays for Future movement, the outputs of the GST might provide an important point of reference and legitimation. However, a condition for that is that the GST elaborates and endorses relatively granular guidelines on where we need to be, not only in 2050 but also in 2030, the corresponding time horizon for subsequent NDCs. The more granular, comprehensive and differentiated those benchmarks are, the more useful they become for stakeholders to assess policy proposals. Since the GST's mandate is limited to "collective progress" and country-specific benchmarks are explicitly precluded, sectoral granularity can be a useful way forward.

Building on a detailed analysis (see annex) of latest climate change mitigation scenarios contained in the global scenario database for the 6th Assessment Report (AR6) of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2022) as well as selected benchmark studies (IEA, 2021; JRC, 2021; Shell, 2021; Teske, 2019), we propose a series of key global-level sectoral performance benchmarks.

The **power sector** is at the forefront of the low-carbon transition, demonstrated by the upscaling of renewable energy technologies and their rapid cost reductions. In addition, action in the power sector has a high priority as it directly enables the successful decarbonisation of the other demand sectors, including heat demands, moving from fossil fuels to clean electricity where possible (e.g. through electric vehicles, heat pumps, electrification of industrial processes, etc.). To achieve the 1.5°C goal, the sector must achieve the following global benchmarks:

- The share of coal in power generation needs to be reduced to (close to) zero by 2030 in developed countries and by 2040 in developing countries at the very latest.
- CO₂ emissions per unit of electricity need to be reduced to ~150 grCO₂/kWh in 2030, and zero before 2050.
- The share of renewables in electricity generation should increase to about 50% in 2030 and further to 70-80% in 2050. Some scenarios (e.g. IEA) even project renewable energy shares to increase to more than 90% by 2050 assuming limited use of other low-emission options.

The **energy-intensive raw material industries** are often considered to be particularly hard to abate. Key challenges include the limited availability and high costs of low-emission options, while increased energy costs may also raise competitiveness issues leading to trade losses in international markets. Massive research and development for, and upscaling of new decarbonisation options is required. Where electrification of industrial processes is not possible, technologies such as hydrogen-based direct reduced iron, hydrogen as a feedstock for the chemical industry, CCS, CCU, synthetic fuels, or industrial symbiosis need to be initiated before 2030. Overall, to meet the 1.5°C goal:

- Emissions from the industry sector must decline by about 27% by 2030 and 70% by 2050 relative to 2010 levels; some scenarios even achieve close to 100% decline.
- The share of electricity in energy consumption of industry needs to increase to around 30% in 2030 and further to 50% in 2050.

The **transport sector** needs to reverse historic trends with rapidly increasing transport-related emissions as a result of rapid motorisation globally, growing mobility activity and transport volumes, and heavy reliance on oil products. This can be achieved by a combination of reducing induced mobility needs (avoid), using more sustainable and efficient modes of transport (shift) and improving technical efficiency and converting to efficient low-carbon fuels such as electricity and hydrogen/synthetic fuels where necessary (improve). For a 1.5°C compatible pathway:

- Despite rapidly increasing motorisation rates and mobility activity, global transport CO₂ emissions must stabilise at current levels through 2030 and decline to -50% by 2050 relative to 2010, achieving close to 90-100% reduction in some scenarios.
- The share of electricity in total transport energy consumption needs to quintuple to more than 5% in 2030 and further increase to 15-30% by 2050 (close to 50% in some scenarios). Specifically, the share of non-fossil fuels in domestic-only transport energy consumption (electricity, hydrogen, synthetic fuels) should increase close to 90-100% by 2050.

The **buildings sector** is set for a rapid expansion, especially in developing countries as a result of increasing income, improved living standards and comfort, and population growth. To be compatible with the 1.5°C goal:

- CO₂ emissions from buildings must decline by 25% by 2030 from 2010 levels, and 70% in 2050. Recent net-zero scenarios from international organisations suggest even larger reductions of 90-100% by 2050.
- The share of electricity in buildings' energy consumption must increase rapidly from the current 30% to about 45% in 2030 and further to 65-70% in 2050.

Agriculture, forestry and land-use (AFOLU) contribute to climate change in diverse ways. Agriculture (A) sub-sector is a source of GHG emissions, while the Forestry and Other Land Use (FOLU) sub-sector is both a source and a sink of GHGs. Land-based mitigation options received increased attention including by the IPCC (2018a) because of its CO₂ removal potential. Yet, our analysis shows that when considering the net emissions and removals of CO₂ and non-CO₂ gases, AFOLU remains a source for 2030 and 2050 even in ambitious 1.5°C scenarios due to non-CO₂ emissions. The complexities of the AFOLU sector are poorly represented in integrated assessment models, and historical and present emissions data are still not good enough, although new harmonised datasets are emerging that could be used in coming years to improve predictions and align bottom-up and top-down estimates (Grassi et al., 2022). Despite significant uncertainties, it is clear that significant afforestation is required to leverage the sink potential. To achieve the 1.5°C goal:

- ~1.2 million ha of land per year are required for net afforestation up to 2030, and ~2 million ha per year from 2030 to 2050. Though, some 2°C scenarios rely more heavily on the sink potential of forests and require up to 8 million ha of land annually by 2050.

Obviously, a global temperature goal cannot unambiguously be translated into individual actions at the sectoral level. Different strategies and routes could be used to meet the long-term goal, for instance by assigning more reductions to specific sectors, as long as the overall emissions budget is met (since the overall carbon budget determines the long-term temperature change). However, the degree of freedom is limited, as the available emissions budget is small, especially if we consider the 1.5°C goal. In the long run, the differences between sectors disappear and all sectors need to reach net zero emissions eventually.

We recommend that the synthesis report on the outcome of the technical assessment component of the GST includes global sector performance benchmarks based on the above analysis or other best available science. Moreover, we recommend that Parties endorse those performance benchmarks also during the political consideration of outputs and include a clear reference to those benchmarks in the final COP decision or political declaration.

Enhancing International Cooperation

Apart from informing national actions and supporting subsequent NDCs, the GST has also been mandated to inform the enhancement of international cooperation. This refers both to international cooperation under the UNFCCC (e.g., under the umbrella of Article 6), as well as cooperation outside of its auspices. In addition to the UNFCCC and the Paris Agreement, a growing number of inter- and transnational institutions govern various aspects of climate change, many of which address specific sectoral issues. The question is how to harness this broader global climate governance landscape to support sectoral climate action and the achievement of the Paris Agreement's long-term goals (Betsill et al., 2015).

Encourage systematic reporting of sectoral transformation challenges

Within the UNFCCC, we have identified one particular gap. Transforming sectoral systems to the extent necessary is extremely hard and developed and developing countries alike routinely face economic, financial, technical, political/institutional or capacity-related challenges. However, these challenges are not systematically evaluated and reported under either the existing UNFCCC reporting and review system or the Paris Agreement's enhanced transparency framework (Jeffery et al., 2021). Including such information systematically at the level of key sectoral systems in Parties' biennial transparency reports would enable to identify shared challenges, discern effective policies and measures to overcome specific transformation challenges, and thus enable learning. This, in turn, could form an important input into the GST.

We therefore recommend that Parties should voluntarily report on sectoral transformation challenges they are facing. Moreover, Parties should call for a revision of the reporting requirements to include a mandate for Parties to systematically report sector-specific transformation challenges including economic, financial, technical, political/institutional and capacity-related barriers.³

Leverage global governance to address transformation barriers and enablers sector by sector

As at the national level, a sectoral perspective is also helpful to identify how international cooperation can work most effectively. A sectoral perspective allows to pinpoint enablers and barriers and thereby makes it possible to identify the most promising route of action. Yet, significant potential for global governance remains underexploited (Rayner et al., 2021). Distilling key international enablers and shared transformation barriers from the material

³ The formal revision of the Modalities, Procedures and Guidelines for the Enhanced Transparency Framework are only due to be revised in 2027. This, however, would be too late to have an effect on the second Global Stocktake scheduled for 2028.

gathered in the ICP and TD phases of the GST may provide inspiration and legitimation for other international institutions to enhance their governance approaches tailored to the specific needs and opportunities of each sector. Table 1 below illustrates this by listing options for enhanced global governance for the steel industry and transport sector.

We therefore recommend that the outputs of the GST should identify and summarise key opportunities for sectoral climate governance sector by sector and call on other international organisations to exploit the identified opportunities as appropriate.

Table 1 Selected options for enhanced international cooperation in the steelmaking and transport. *Synthesised from Hermwille et al (2022) and Obergassel et al. (2021).*

Steel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • establishing a credible labelling or certification scheme for low-emission steel, combined with an independent auditing and compliance mechanism; • creation of lead markets through coordinated public and private procurement and dynamic but limited subsidies enabled through carbon contracts for difference; • an international moratorium on (re-)investments in conventional unabated steel making facilities from e.g. 2025
Transport	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International coordination of vehicle regulations and phase-out dates for conventional vehicles to accelerate market transformation. • Provision of international support for developing countries to establish the necessary charging infrastructure and improve electricity supply to cope with increasing loads and shifts in the demand profile. • Generally, shift all international financing from high-emission to low-emission transport modes.

Align activities by sectoral institutions and organisations with Paris goals

International cooperation at the sectoral level consists of a variety of informal cooperative initiatives through which sectoral emissions are addressed, involving governments, businesses and other actors (e.g., the Industrial Deep Decarbonisation Initiative, the Forest Declaration Platform, the SLOCAT Partnership on Sustainable Low Carbon Transport). However, some sectoral emissions are directly addressed by other intergovernmental institutions. The most prominent of these are emissions from international aviation and international shipping, which are tackled by the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) and International Maritime Organization (IMO) respectively. Some progress has been made in these institutions. The IMO has adopted an Initial GHG Strategy, which aims for a 40% reduction in carbon intensity by 2030 and pursuing efforts towards a 70% reduction by 2050 (compared to 2008 levels). Moreover, the organisation has adopted several short-term measures, including an Energy Efficiency Ship Index and a carbon intensity reduction requirement for shipowners. Although ICAO has not set a long-term target – one is under consideration at its next Assembly in September 2022 – it adopted a market-based mechanism – the Carbon Offsetting and Reduction Scheme for International Aviation (CORSIA) – in 2016. Although both ICAO and IMO regularly submit statements and reports to the UNFCCC, these do not include any indication of how the efforts by these institutions contribute to the long-term goals of the Paris Agreement, even though emissions in these two sectors are projected to increase significantly in the coming decades.

We therefore recommend that Parties to the Paris Agreement use the GST to send a signal to other intergovernmental institutions by requesting periodic reports in which these institutions indicate not only what measures have been adopted, but also how those measures are aligned with the Paris Agreement’s long-term goals.

References

- Betsill, M. M., Dubash, N. K., Paterson, M., van Asselt, H., Vihma, A., & Winkler, H. (2015). Building Productive Links between the UNFCCC and the Broader Global Climate Governance Landscape. *Global Environmental Politics*, 15(2), 1–10. https://doi.org/10.1162/GLEP_a_00294
- Beuermann, C., Obergassel, W., van Asselt, H., Häntzschel, M., & Petersmann, M. (2021). Maximising the Impact of the Global Stocktake: Options for Design and Implementation [NDC ASPECTS Policy Brief]. Wuppertal Institute for Climate, Environment and Energy & University of Eastern Finland. https://www.ndc-aspects.eu/sites/default/files/2021-10/GST_Policy_Brief_fin.pdf
- Briand, Y., & Waisman, H. (2019). Enhancing the ambition of NDCs through the analysis of sectoral transformations: The example of freight transport (Issue Brief No. 14/19; p. 4). IDDRI. <https://www.iddri.org/en/publications-and-events/issue-brief/enhancing-ambition-ndcs-through-analysis-sectoral>
- Churkina, G., Organschi, A., Reyer, C. P. O., Ruff, A., Vinke, K., Liu, Z., Reck, B. K., Graedel, T. E., & Schellnhuber, H. J. (2020). Buildings as a global carbon sink. *Nature Sustainability*, 3(4), 269–276. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-019-0462-4>
- Fazekas, A., Bataille, C., & Vogt-Schilb, A. (2022). Achieving Net-Zero Prosperity: How Governments Can Unlock 15 Essential Transformations (2022nd ed.). IDDRI, IDB. <https://doi.org/10.18235/0004364>
- Grassi, G., Conchedda, G., Federici, S., Abad Viñas, R., Korosuo, A., Melo, J., Rossi, S., Sandker, M., Somogyi, Z., & Tubiello, F. N. (2022). Carbon fluxes from land 2000-2020: Bringing clarity on countries' reporting (pp. 1–49) [Earth System Science Data]. Copernicus GmbH. <https://essd.copernicus.org/preprints/essd-2022-104/>
- Griscom, B. W., Adams, J., Ellis, P. W., Houghton, R. A., Lomax, G., Miteva, D. A., Schlesinger, W. H., Shoch, D., Siikamäki, J. V., Smith, P., Woodbury, P., Zganjar, C., Blackman, A., Campari, J., Conant, R. T., Delgado, C., Elias, P., Gopalakrishna, T., Hamsik, M. R., ... Fargione, J. (2017). Natural climate solutions. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 114(44), 11645–11650. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1710465114>
- Hermwille, L., Lechtenböhmer, S., Åhman, M., van Asselt, H., Bataille, C., Kronshage, S., Tönjes, A., Fishedick, M., Oberthür, S., Garg, A., Hall, C., Jochem, P., Schneider, C., Cui, R., Obergassel, W., Fragkos, P., Sudharmma Vishwanathan, S., & Trollip, H. (2022). A climate club to decarbonize the global steel industry. *Nature Climate Change*, 12, 494–496. <https://doi.org/10/gp664g>
- IEA. (2021). World Energy Outlook 2021. International Energy Agency. <https://www.iea.org/reports/world-energy-outlook-2021>
- IPCC. (2018a). Climate Change and Land: An IPCC special report on climate change, desertification, land degradation, sustainable land management, food security, and greenhouse gas fluxes in terrestrial ecosystems. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). <https://www.ipcc.ch/srcl/download/>
- IPCC. (2018b). Global Warming of 1.5°C – Summary for Policy Makers. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). http://www.ipcc.ch/pdf/special-reports/sr15/sr15_spm_final.pdf
- IPCC. (2022). Climate Change 2022: Mitigation of Climate Change. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). https://report.ipcc.ch/ar6wg3/pdf/IPCC_AR6_WGIII_FinalDraft_FullReport.pdf
- JRC. (2021). Global energy and climate outlook 2021: Advancing towards climate neutrality : taking stock of climate policy pledges after COP26 and the corresponding energy economy implications. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/410610>
- Milkoreit, M., & Haapala, K. (2018). The global stocktake: Design lessons for a new review and ambition mechanism in the international climate regime. *International Environmental Agreements: Politics, Law and Economics*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10784-018-9425-x>
- Obergassel, W., Lah, O., & Rudolph, F. (2021). Driving towards transformation? To what extent does global climate governance promote decarbonisation of land transport? *Earth System Governance*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esg.2021.100098>
- Oberthür, S., Hermwille, L., & Rayner, T. (2021). A sectoral perspective on global climate governance: Analytical foundation. *Earth System Governance*, 8, 100104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esg.2021.100104>

- Peterson, L., van Asselt, H., Hermwille, L., & Oberthür, S. (forthcoming). The Determinants of Ambition? Analysing NDC Enhancement with a Mixed-method Design (NDC ASPECTS Deliverable D4.1).
- Rayner, T., Oberthür, S., & Hermwille, L. (2021). A sectoral perspective on international climate governance: Key findings and research priorities. *Earth System Governance*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esg.2021.100105>
- Roe, S., Streck, C., Obersteiner, M., Frank, S., Griscom, B., Drouet, L., Fricko, O., Gusti, M., Harris, N., Hasegawa, T., Hausfather, Z., Havlík, P., House, J., Nabuurs, G.-J., Popp, A., Sánchez, M. J. S., Sanderman, J., Smith, P., Stehfest, E., & Lawrence, D. (2019). Contribution of the land sector to a 1.5 °C world. *Nature Climate Change*, 9(11), 817–828. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-019-0591-9>
- Shell. (2021). The Energy Transformation Scenarios. <https://www.shell.com/transformationsscenarios>
- SLOCAT. (2021). Climate Strategies for Transport: An Analysis of Nationally Determined Contributions and Long-Term Strategies. Partnership for Sustainable, Low Carbon Transport. <https://slocat.net/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/Climate-Strategies-for-Transport-An-Analysis-of-NDCs-and-LTS-SLOCAT-December-2021.pdf>
- Teske, S. (2019). Achieving the paris climate agreement goals: Global and regional 100% renewable energy scenarios with non-energy GHG pathways for +1.5c and +2c. Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- Torres Gunfaus, M., & Waisman, H. (2021). Assessing the adequacy of the global response to the Paris Agreement: Toward a full appraisal of climate ambition and action. *Earth System Governance*, 8, 100102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esg.2021.100102>
- Ürge-Vorsatz, D., Khosla, R., Bernhardt, R., Chan, Y. C., Vérez, D., Hu, S., & Cabeza, L. F. (2020). Advances Toward a Net-Zero Global Building Sector. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 45(1), 227–269. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-012420-045843>
- Victor, D. G., Geels, F. W., & Sharpe, S. (2019). Accelerating the Low Carbon Transition – The case for stronger, more targeted and coordinated international action (p. 140). www.energy-transitions.org/sites/default/files/Accelerating-The-Transitions_Report.pdf

ANNEX: Detailed Analysis of Key Global Sector Benchmarks

Based on a detailed assessment of the latest climate change mitigation scenarios contained in the scenario database for the 6th Assessment Report (AR6) of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2022), representing the best available science today, and key international benchmark studies from international organisations, industry and academia (IEA, 2021; JRC, 2021; Shell, 2021; Teske, 2019), we propose a series of key global-level sectoral performance benchmarks.

The Paris Agreement's temperature goal means that all sectors and countries will eventually have to reduce emissions to net-zero, with the main questions being when and how. To inform policy improvements and to monitor the state of transformational change – whether it is already underway, or more action is required – we need more granular information. Sectoral indicators and benchmarks allow us to track the various elements of action that together will allow us to meet the Paris Agreement's global temperature goal as set out in the Paris Agreement. These sectoral benchmarks speak more closely to those making the relevant decisions and help to map out Paris-compatible pathways in more detail.

We have defined and analysed a global-level series of Paris-compatible benchmarks, across five major sectors: Power, Transport, Industry, Buildings, and AFOLU. Within each sector, we define benchmarks for several separate but complementary indicators, focusing on both 2030 and 2050, based on information and data derived from the scenario database of the IPCC 6th AR6 Assessment Report (IPCC, 2022). We define detailed Paris-compatible sectoral benchmarks as a level of an indicator that would be “sufficient” for climate action to decarbonise sectors in line with the Paris Agreement's 1.5°C temperature limit. The sectoral benchmarks should be technically and economically feasible within the foreseeable future, considering current circumstances, including social aspects, and should push boundaries on all levels and increase our chances of collectively meeting the Paris temperature limit. These benchmarks should prioritise mitigation options that lead to the deepest and fastest emission reductions, but should also include other options that we are confident are feasible, based on the current development of technologies and the time taken to make changes to existing stock, infrastructure or to scale-up new technologies. These benchmarks can be reached through various decarbonisation routes and mitigation options.

The Power Sector

The electricity sector is at the forefront of the low-carbon transition, demonstrated by the upscaling of renewable energy technologies combined with their rapid cost reductions. In addition, action in the power sector has a high priority as it directly enables the successful decarbonisation of the demand sectors, including heat demands, moving from fossil fuels to clean electricity where possible (e.g. through electric vehicles, heat pumps, electrification of industrial processes etc). Coal phase-out should be the top priority, as coal is by far the most carbon-intensive option to generate electricity. In Paris-compatible scenarios, coal's share in power generation needs to be reduced to (close to) zero by 2030 in developed countries and by 2040 at the very latest in emerging economies where coal currently dominates the electricity supply. In all countries, CO₂ emissions per unit of electricity produced need to be rapidly reduced from about 550 grCO₂/kWh in 2010 to about 150 grCO₂/kWh in 1.5C-compatible scenarios in 2030, and then they should reach zero ideally before 2050, and even turn “negative” in 2050 (see figure below), depending on the availability and emergence of Carbon Dioxide Removal options, in particular BECCS.

Renewables need to be ramped up at a rapidly accelerated pace to deliver emissions-free electricity before 2050 in Paris-compatible scenarios. The share of renewables in electricity generation should increase from 20% in 2010 to about 50% in 2030 according to Paris-compatible scenarios and further to 70-80% in 2050 according to IPCC scenario results. Other scenarios from international organisations (e.g. IEA) are even more ambitious, projecting renewable energy shares increasing to more than 90% by 2050, especially when other low-emission options (e.g. nuclear, carbon capture and storage (CCS)) face limitations. From all emissions-free options, renewables seem to be the most viable given the rapid reduction in their costs and fast technology developments. Variable renewable energy sources can be backed with storage options, the production of synthetic gas or hydrogen from renewable electricity and its use e.g. in power-reconversion, expansion of electricity grids, end-use flexibility options and smart grid developments. CCS options combined with fossil fuels gain limited shares, because CCS itself is not emissions free and (given current technology cost trends) CCS is already or soon will be uneconomic compared to renewables with storage. The current generation of nuclear power plants is not flexible enough for cost-effective system integration with high shares of renewable energy, while further deployment of nuclear faces serious acceptance and licensing issues as well as cost overruns in several countries worldwide.

The Industry Sector

The industry sector – and especially the energy-intensive manufacturing processes to produce steel, cement, chemicals, paper and pulp – is often considered as the hardest to abate sector, due to limited availability and high costs of low-emission options, while increased energy costs may also raise competitiveness issues leading to trade losses in international markets. Our analysis shows that the key decarbonisation benchmarks are: accelerated efficiency improvements (e.g. heat recovery, using best available technologies, etc.), to ensure compatibility with the 1.5°C goal, emissions from the industry sector should decline by about 27% by 2030 and 70% by 2050 relative to 2010 levels, while reductions can even reach close to 100% in net-zero scenarios from international organisations. Mitigation scenarios also incorporate enhanced material efficiency and large reductions in energy intensity of industrial production, as using less steel or cement can result in further emissions reductions and also allows low-carbon technologies (mostly electricity and hydrogen) to cover higher shares of final energy demand. Electrification of industry needs to increase from about 20% in 2010 to around 30% in 2030 and further to 50% in 1.5°C scenarios in 2050. For some industrial processes, electrification provides a key potential route for decarbonisation when accompanied by low-emission electricity. Not all industrial production processes can be electrified, and thus other approaches for decarbonisation should be considered (e.g. hydrogen, CCS/CCU). This heterogeneity of industry actors makes a sector-specific consideration of industry in GST obvious.

The Transport Sector

In Paris-compatible scenarios, the transport sector is set for a major transformation away from the current oil-dominant paradigm. In contrast to historic trends with rapidly increasing transport-related emissions as a result of rapid motorisation globally, growing mobility activity and transport volumes, and heavy reliance on oil products, Paris-compatible scenarios from the IPCC AR6 show that global transport CO₂ emissions should – after decades of significant growth – decline by about 50% in 1.5°C-compatible scenarios over the 2010-2050 period. Most of the remaining transport-related emissions in 2050 come from the aviation and maritime sectors, which have a limited number of decarbonisation options and face challenges in the upscaling of low-emission fuels. The required emission reduction is even larger and amounts to 90-100% below 2010 levels in net-zero scenarios from international organisations.

Despite rapidly increasing motorisation rates and mobility activity by 2050, final energy demand in Paris-compatible scenarios is projected to increase by only 15% by 2030 and 10% by 2050 from 2010 levels (while even declining in some net-zero scenarios) pointing towards increasing energy efficiency in all vehicles and transportation modes (cars, trucks, ships, planes), combined with the emergence of more efficient energy forms. In particular the share of electricity in the transport sector is set for a rapid increase from the current less than 1% to more than 5% in 2030 and further to 15-30% by 2050, while electricity share is found even larger (close to 50% by 2050) in scenarios from international organisations, as a result of the massive uptake of electric vehicles that reach very high market shares already by 2030 and even more in 2050. The share of sustainable non-fossil fuels (electricity, hydrogen, synthetic fuels) for domestic transport should increase close to 90-100% by 2050 in net-zero scenarios, but given the technological difficulties in achieving full decarbonisation in shipping and aviation, most 2050 benchmarks for the share of low emission fuels in transport do not reach 100%. Overall, decarbonising transportation is heading for a tough time as a reversion of the current emissions trend is mandatory. Mitigation options could be very country specific, which makes a sector-specific consideration in the GST process valuable.

The Buildings Sector

The buildings sector is set for a rapid expansion, especially in developing countries as a result of increasing income, improved living standards and comfort, and population growth. However, to be compatible with the 1.5°C goal, CO₂ emissions from buildings should decline by 25% by 2030 from 2010 levels, while the reduction is even larger in 2050 (about 70%). Recent net-zero scenarios from the IEA suggest even larger reductions of 90-100% by 2050. The main technical emission reduction options in the sector include: 1) accelerated reduction of energy intensity of the building stock (e.g. through renovation and high thermal building standards); 2) a rapid shift to low carbon heating, cooling, and cooking (e.g. heat pumps, district heating/cooling, the direct use of renewable energy); 3) further efficiency improvements of appliances and equipment which are key to keeping energy demand and emissions low while providing adequate living standards. In particular, the share of electricity in buildings' energy consumption is projected to increase rapidly from the current 30% to about 45% in 1.5°C scenarios in 2030 and further to 65-70% in 2050, both accordingly to the IPCC AR6 scenario database and the key international benchmarks studies.

Moreover, embodied energy and emissions in building materials will play an increasingly important role when buildings become more efficient (Ürge-Vorsatz et al., 2020). Embodied emissions can be reduced by using low-carbon materials, re-using building materials, and extending life-time of building components (Churkina et al., 2020). Finally, especially in developed countries demand side measures are required to enable sufficient forms of living and curb growth in per-capita floor space. On the global scale – but also within nations – the building stock is highly diverse, which makes a sector-specific consideration in the GST indispensable.

The AFOLU sector

In the AFOLU sector, the Agriculture (A) sub-sector is a source of GHG emissions, while the Forestry and Other Land Use (FOLU) sub-sector is both a source and a sink of GHGs. The FOLU sub-sector is often considered to have a large potential for mitigation at low cost (Griscom et al., 2017; Roe et al., 2019). Land-based mitigation options received increased attention by IPCC e.g., through the Special Report on Climate Change and Land (IPCC, 2018a), precisely because of its CO₂ removal potential. Our analysis shows that when considering the net emissions and removals of CO₂ and non-CO₂ gases, AFOLU remains a source for 2030 and 2050 for both scenarios due to non-CO₂ emissions. On the other hand, among the options considered net afforestation show a large potential but will require a large amount of land for its deployment in particular for scenarios under 2°C by 2050 of 8 million hectares (ha) per year on average (although with very large uncertainties) and half or it by 2030. Instead, under 1.5°C scenarios the land required for net afforestation is about 2 million ha per year for both 2030 and 2050, showing less reliance on this mitigation measure. Overall, emission measures to reduce methane in agriculture combined with reducing deforestation and increasing forest cover seem to be the most promising options considered. The FOLU sub-sector needs to become a significant net sink by 2050 under both 2°C and 1.5°C scenarios. Although, 1.5°C scenarios rely less on the sub-sector’s sink potential compared to the analysed 2°C scenarios. Yet, overall, the AFOLU sector will remain a net emitter by 2030. The complexities of the AFOLU sector are poorly represented in integrated assessment models, and historical and present emissions are still not good enough, although new harmonised datasets are emerging that could be used in coming years to improve predictions and align bottom-up and top-down estimates (Grassi et al., 2022).

AFOLU

Challenges in Determining Sectoral Benchmarks

The main challenge in defining the sectoral benchmarks is that a global temperature goal cannot unambiguously be translated into individual actions at the sectoral level. Different strategies and routes could be used to meet the long-term goal, for instance by assigning more reductions to specific sectors, as long as the overall emissions budget is met (since the overall carbon budget determines the long-term temperature change). However, the degree of freedom is limited, as the available emissions budget is small, especially if we consider the 1.5°C goal. It is clear that all sectors and countries will eventually have to reduce emissions close to net zero. So, if one sector is slower than this global trend, another sector needs to be equivalently faster, or emissions need to be removed from the atmosphere through the upscale of CDR technologies, which however are commercially immature, expensive and face large technical, environmental and societal risks. A good starting point can be to ask whether a sector can decarbonise by 2050, and if not, why? In this situation the differences between sectors disappear in the long run, because all need to reach net zero emissions. Even if the endpoint is the same, the transition dynamics and the speed of transformation can be very different across sectors.

The benchmarks consider the extent to which each sector needs to be decarbonised to be compatible with the Paris Agreement, irrespective of who pays for this transition. The very limited carbon budget - in particular for the 1.5°C goal - does not leave much room for some countries to decarbonise more slowly. As the Paris Agreement requires decarbonisation by mid-century there will be a need for financial transfers and other support between countries (e.g. technology transfer, capacity building), to ensure a fair and just transition. The extent of this support and how it can be achieved is beyond the scope of this analysis. Nevertheless, some aspects of fairness are implicitly considered when determining the benchmarks, especially as these are included in IPCC scenarios, e.g. focus on convergence of efficiencies and shares (e.g. share of renewables, emissions per activity), while end-use activities might be growing much faster in developing economies than in developed countries. However, as the focus is on global benchmarks, the equity issue is not explicitly considered here.

Synthesis

Overall, achieving the objectives of the Paris Agreement requires the world to decarbonise by 2050. Our analysis shows that on average all sectors need to decarbonise by mid-century (or slightly after), albeit at different rates. The electricity sector is relatively advanced and is already making quite some progress towards decarbonising, mostly through the rapid deployment and upscaling of renewable energy (wind and solar PV). The sector should continue to be a government priority, especially in avoiding new infrastructure incompatible with the Paris Agreement, such as coal-fired power plants. Industry, transport, buildings need to advance significantly: these sectors are not yet moving as quickly as is necessary to meet Paris goals, and efforts to meet 2030 benchmarks must significantly ramp up. Accelerated electrification of end-uses in transport, buildings and industries combined with carbon-free power supply is a key strategy to reduce emissions across sectors. The FOLU sub-sector needs to become a significant net sink by 2050 under both 2°C and 1.5°C scenarios. Although, 1.5°C scenarios rely less on the sub-sector's sink potential compared to the analysed 2°C scenarios. Yet, overall, the AFOLU sector will remain a net emitter by 2030. In terms of timing, benchmarks differ between sectors, because they all start from a different baseline. But ultimately, differences between sectors shrink over time and governments must pursue all options in all sectors, and sometimes this will require international support between countries. The sectoral benchmarks are useful tools to assess and monitor the progress of national policies and NDCs towards meeting the Paris goals. Policymakers and public authorities can use the benchmarks to assess the adequacy of policy interventions with

respect to the Paris Agreement. Our benchmarks provide a guide as to the scale of change that needs to happen, and where - and when, leaving governments the freedom to meet them through different decarbonisation strategies. Finally, our analysis shows that progress by 2030 is important, as decarbonisation by 2050 alone is not sufficient; to keep the ambitious carbon budgets – and associated temperature targets – within reach, progress must ramp up well before 2030 pointing towards the need for revising and significantly enhancing the ambition of NDCs, while stronger and more reliable policies should be put in place to allow achieving these enhanced NDCs and long-term low-emission development strategies.

NDC ASPECTS

SUBMISSION TO THE GLOBAL STOCKTAKE

Ensuring an Effective Global Stocktake with a Sectoral Perspective

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